

Co-cultivation of lactic acid bacteria and fodder yeasts for probiotics and postbiotics production on halophyte-based hydrolysate

Stanislav Rudnycky^{a,*}, Oriol Varon Morales^b, Paula Ramirez Sanchez Aguilera^b, Sara Brandolini^b, Steinunn Leifsdóttir^b, Mette Hedegaard Thomsen^b

^a Aalborg University, Department of Energy, Niels Bohrs Vej 8, 6700 Esbjerg, Denmark

^b Aalborg University, Department of Chemistry and Bioscience, Niels Bohrs Vej 8, 6700 Esbjerg, Denmark

HIGHLIGHTS

- Co-cultivation outperformed single strains on halophyte media.
- Natural yeast deacidification improved growth and product yields.
- *Bacillus coagulans* boosted protein and B12 in co-culture.
- *K. marxianus* DSM 7238 and *S. cerevisiae* showed top performance in co-cultures.
- Yeast detoxified media, enabling other microbes to thrive.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Halophyte
Robust yeast
Lactic acid bacteria
Co-cultivation
Postbiotics
Second-generation feedstock

ABSTRACT

This study explores the potential of probiotic bacteria-yeast co-cultivation to enhance microbial growth and postbiotic production using halophyte-based media. Initial screening of six yeast strains revealed variations in nutrient utilization, with *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, *Kluyveromyces marxianus* DSM 7238, and *Cyberlindnera jadinii* DSM 2361, demonstrating superior carbon source consumption and biomass production. Co-cultivation with *Bacillus coagulans* ATCC 7050 enhanced overall product formation, whereas *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum* DSM 13272 had undesirable effects on product formation. Optimization trials demonstrated that increasing the total inoculum size to 10 % (v/v) and extending cultivation to 72 h significantly enhanced product yields in selected bacteria-yeast co-cultures, enabling complete utilization of the available carbon sources. Specifically, the best performing combination of *B. coagulans* ATCC 7050 and *K. marxianus* DSM 7238 achieved 17.5 g of cell dry weight, 6.9 g of crude protein, and 42.2 mg of vitamin B12/L in halophyte-based broth. Advanced statistical analysis revealed that yeast-driven deacidification played a critical role in improving culture conditions, reducing organic acid stress, and promoting microbial growth. The findings suggest that bacteria-yeast interactions in co-cultures under non-sterile conditions contribute to enhanced fermentation efficiency, with yeast potentially acting as a detoxifier. This study underscores the viability of bacteria-yeast co-cultivation for sustainable probiotics and postbiotics production using halophyte hydrolysate as a production medium and lays the

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: stru@energy.aau.dk (S. Rudnycky).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2025.133240>

Received 11 July 2025; Received in revised form 7 August 2025; Accepted 27 August 2025

Available online 27 August 2025

0960-8524/© 2025 The Author(s). Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

groundwork for future process optimization and industrial-scale applications in alternative protein and nutraceutical development.

1. Introduction

The increasing global interest in probiotics and postbiotics is reflected in the growing market for these supplements. For example, the global probiotic market is currently valued at approximately 73 billion USD and is projected to reach 85 billion USD by 2027 (Shahbandeh, 2025). Additionally, the nutraceutical industry had an estimated global market value of 591 billion USD in 2024 and is forecasted to grow at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of approximately 7.6 % from 2025 to 2030 (GVR, 2025). This expansion is driven by rising consumer awareness of health and wellness, along with a growing preference for “natural” and “traditional” alternatives over synthetic-based products (Cosme et al., 2022; Nguyen et al., 2020). This requirement could be partly covered by probiotics and postbiotics produced from halophyte-based biorefineries (Rudnyckij and Thomsen, 2025), thereby fulfilling consumer preferences for greener alternatives while contributing to both the circular economy (Accogli et al., 2023; Yadav et al., 2018) and regenerative agriculture (Ahmadi et al., 2022; Aziz and Mujeeb, 2022).

Halophytes are salt-tolerant plants capable of thriving in diverse environments, including marshes, deserts, and coastal regions, from the tropics to the arctic (Flowers and Colmer, 2008). Their adaptability is linked to unique biochemical pathways (Ksouri et al., 2008), which enable them to produce high concentrations of bioactive compounds with nutraceutical applications, including polyphenols, antioxidants, flavonoids, and vitamins (Giordano et al., 2021; Hulkko et al., 2022a). A halophyte-based biorefinery primarily focuses on extracting these high-value bioactive compounds (Fredsgaard et al., 2023; Hulkko et al., 2023), while the remaining biomass, composed of residual materials such as halophyte juice and lignocellulosic fibers, can be repurposed into various by-products, including biogas (Cayenne et al., 2022), bioethanol or bulk chemicals (Cybulska et al., 2014; Fredsgaard et al., 2021; Monção et al., 2023, 2022), and protein concentrates (Christiansen et al., 2021; Hulkko, 2023). However, rather than being used solely for biofuels or bulk chemicals production, these residues hold potential for creating higher-value products such as nutraceuticals, specifically probiotics and postbiotics (Rudnyckij and Thomsen, 2025). Microbial fermentation, using specific bacteria and fungi, can convert plant biomass into valuable products, including probiotic strains themselves (Alassali et al., 2017; Babich et al., 2024; Hanif et al., 2024). This approach not only reduces waste but also enhances the overall efficiency of the biorefinery process. Moreover, microbial fermentation can improve nutrient digestibility and bioavailability in saline plant-derived biomasses, increasing their functional value for human and animal health (Salgado et al., 2021; Saritaş et al., 2024).

Bacterial genera such as *Lactobacillus*, *Lactococcus*, *Bacillus*, and *Bifidobacterium* (Fijan, 2014; Khushboo et al., 2023; Maftai et al., 2024), along with yeast genera like *Saccharomyces* (Czerucka et al., 2007) and *Kluyveromyces* (Moradi et al., 2018), have been widely recognized for their beneficial effects on gut health and overall human well-being. Additionally, generally recognized as safe (GRAS) non-*Saccharomyces* yeasts have shown potential as probiotics, particularly for animal feed applications (Vergara et al., 2023). Notable examples include *Cyberlindnera jadinii* (formerly known as *Candida utilis*) (Hugot et al., 2023) and *Yarrowia lipolytica* (Keskin et al., 2024), among others. Moreover, their health benefits to a large extent originate from the diverse bioactive metabolites, including organic acids (Moradi et al., 2021; Morrison and Preston, 2016; Ponzio et al., 2024), exopolysaccharides (Aggarwal et al., 2022), vitamins (Bourebaba et al., 2022; Sadeghi et al., 2022), fragments of cell wall (Da et al., 2024), enzymes (Maske et al., 2021), and antimicrobial peptides (Mejía-Pitta et al., 2021) are classified as postbiotics.

Generally, probiotics are defined as “live microorganisms which confer a health benefit on the host” (Hill et al., 2014), while postbiotics are defined as “their components that confer a health benefit on the host” (Salminen et al., 2021). In this study, postbiotics refer to bioactive microbial metabolites such as vitamin B12, organic acids (lactic and acetic acid), and proteins, which are commonly associated with gut health benefits and functional food applications. Vitamin B12 is a well-known health-promoting compound with recognized therapeutic and nutritional benefits (Kumar et al., 2023). Organic acids such as acetic and lactic acid are also widely acknowledged as postbiotics due to their antimicrobial properties and roles in maintaining intestinal health (Mathur et al., 2020; Morrison and Preston, 2016). Although crude protein is not a single defined compound with direct health claims, it represents a major fraction of microbial biomass. As such, it is part of microbial cell fragments, which have been associated with health-promoting effects (Akter et al., 2020). Moreover, dietary crude protein has been demonstrated to promote health and growth in animals when used as a feed additive in cattle (Lean et al., 2012), pigs (Limbach et al., 2021), and aquaculture species (Agboola et al., 2021; Chu and Brown, 2022).

Since halophyte biomass feedstocks are relatively novel and largely unexplored, particularly for probiotics and postbiotics production, only a limited number of studies have demonstrated their potential for these applications. However, some promising findings have emerged. For example, *Salicornia ramosissima* has been utilized as a salt supplement in cabbage fermentation, leading to postbiotic production in form of higher total phenol and antioxidant content, as well as probiotic production evidenced by an increased *Lactobacilli* population compared to the control (Pires-Cabral et al., 2022). Similarly, Maoloni et al. showed that *L. plantarum* IMC 509®, in combination with *L. rhamnosus* IMC 501® and *L. paracasei* IMC 502®, was able to survive and maintain its colony-forming unit (CFU) count for 44 days when cultivated in brined sea fennel (*Crithmum maritimum* L.), supporting the potential of halophytes as probiotic substrates (Maoloni et al., 2022). Additionally, Alassali and colleagues showed that the potential probiotic *S. cerevisiae* exhibited robust growth on *Salicornia sinus-persica* juice, accompanied by the production of postbiotics such as acetic and lactic acids (Alassali et al., 2017). In another study, Hulkko successfully cultivated potential probiotic *L. plantarum* and *L. salivarius* on green juice derived from *S. ramosissima* and *Tripolium pannonicum*, leading to the formation of postbiotics including lactic and acetic acids (Hulkko, 2023). These findings suggest that halophyte juices can serve as viable substrates for *Lactobacillus* cultivation, further supporting their potential role in probiotic and postbiotic production.

Although co-cultivation of GRAS yeasts and LAB is well-established for conventional plant-based feedstocks, halophyte-based hydrolysates present a fundamentally different growth environment. In contrast to grass juice or typical lignocellulosic hydrolysates, halophyte hydrolysates contain elevated salinity, a distinct polyphenolic profile, and naturally occurring antimicrobial metabolites such as flavonoids and phenolic acids. These factors can significantly influence microbial stress tolerance, metabolic regulation, and nutrient assimilation, ultimately shaping probiotic and postbiotic production. To our knowledge, this is the first systematic investigation of GRAS yeast-LAB co-cultivation on halophyte-based hydrolysate.

In the present study, we focused on the co-cultivation of probiotic bacteria and yeast on halophyte-based substrate, drawing inspiration from traditional fermented products where these microorganisms coexist in a natural symbiotic relationship. Examples of such products include sourdough (Pérez-Alvarado et al., 2022), kombucha (Antolak et al., 2021), sauerkraut (Yang et al., 2020), fermented vegetables (Seo

et al., 2020; Xu et al., 2024), kefir (Stadie et al., 2013), cocoa and coffee fermentation (de Oliveira Junqueira et al., 2019; Figueroa-Hernández et al., 2019), as well as fermented beverages like wine and craft beer (Torres-Guardado et al., 2021). The major benefit of co-culturing lies in this natural symbiosis, which has been demonstrated across various traditional fermentations, enhancing flavor, texture, and probiotic potential. This symbiosis can be attributed to several factors: 1) Nutrient exchange: Yeasts can produce essential metabolites, such as vitamins and amino acids, that support bacterial growth, while bacteria, in turn, can provide a carbon source and growth-promoting factors for yeasts (Ponomarova et al., 2017; Sieuwerts et al., 2018; Stadie et al., 2013; Viljoen, 2001); 2) Enhanced stress tolerance: The presence of both microorganisms can improve their resilience to environmental stresses, such as acidity, osmotic pressure, and oxidative stress, which is particularly beneficial in fermentation processes (Sieuwerts et al., 2018; Stadie et al., 2013; Viljoen, 2001; Vorob'eva et al., 2016); 3) Modulation of metabolism: The interaction between bacteria and yeasts can influence metabolic pathways, leading to improved utilization of carbon sources and enhanced production of bioactive compounds (Nguyen et al., 2015; Sieuwerts et al., 2018); 4) Enhanced postbiotics production: Co-cultivation can enhance the production of postbiotics, such as antimicrobial compounds (Pihurov et al., 2023; Zoumpourtikoudi et al., 2018), organic acids (Healy et al., 2023; Pihurov et al., 2023; Zoumpourtikoudi et al., 2018), and exopolysaccharides (Cheirsilp et al., 2003; González-Orozco et al., 2023), which contribute to gut health and the stability of fermented products. By leveraging these advantages, co-cultivation presents a promising strategy for enhancing the functionality and stability of probiotic and postbiotic formulations, particularly when utilizing halophyte-derived substrates.

More specifically, Healy et al. demonstrated that Kombucha SCOBY (Symbiotic Culture of Bacteria and Yeast) cultivated on saline plant-based feedstocks exhibited enhanced production of organic acids, including lactic, tartaric, and acetic acids, compared to pure cultures of *S. cerevisiae* and *L. plantarum* (Healy et al., 2023). Similarly, González-Orozco and coworkers found that *Lactobacillus kefirifaciens* showed increased survival and postbiotic production when co-cultured with *K. marxianus* (González-Orozco et al., 2023). In another study, Liu et al. presented that the co-culture of *Bacillus coagulans* and *C. utilis* exhibited significantly enhanced growth and nutrient utilization compared to individual cultures when cultivated on *Lactobacillus* fermentation wastewater (Liu et al., 2019). Wang and colleagues demonstrated that mixed fermentation with *L. plantarum*, *Bifidobacterium animalis* subsp. *lactis*, and *C. utilis* enhanced fermentation quality compared to control groups, leading to an increased content of bioactive compounds and a reduced fermentation time (Wang et al., 2023). Furthermore, incorporating yeast into bacterial fermentation may enhance the product's digestibility and improve its essential amino acid profile (Salgado et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2017).

Based on the demonstrated symbiotic relationship in previously reported research, we selected various GRAS yeast species, including *S. cerevisiae*, *K. marxianus*, *C. jadinii*, and *Y. lipolytica*, along with probiotic bacteria *B. coagulans* and *L. plantarum*, to evaluate their ability to utilize carbon sources and grow on halophyte-based media. Additionally, parameters such as lactic acid, acetic acid, vitamin B12, and crude protein concentration were analyzed to assess their potential for postbiotic production, as these compounds have demonstrated overall health benefits and are considered nutraceuticals. Firstly, only yeast strains were cultured in the halophyte-based hydrolysate to assess the performance of single cultures. Then, various bacteria-yeast co-cultures were investigated, and the four best-performing combinations were selected for inoculum size and cultivation time optimization using a full factorial experimental design. This resulted in promising yields of cell dry weight, crude protein, and vitamin B12. Lastly, the produced data were subjected to statistical analysis, which demonstrated a strong positive correlation between pH and both cell growth and protein content, suggesting that the yeast's ability to deacidify the medium is a key driver

for product generation. In summary, this study highlights the benefits of bacteria-yeast co-culture on microbial growth and overall postbiotic production using halophyte-based hydrolysate as the medium, identifying key factors contributing to the co-culture's strong performance.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Halophyte-based materials

The green biomass of *S. ramosissima* was cultivated and collected on the 9th and 10th of October 2023 by Riasearch. The halophyte biomass was fractionated on the 12th of October 2023 at the demonstration-scale grass processing facility, Aarhus University in Foulum, Denmark. The same day, the produced green juice was stored at -20°C until needed. Before use, green juice was defrosted at room temperature (19°C) and centrifuged (SL 16 Centrifuge, Thermo Fisher Scientific) at 4500 RPM for 10 min to separate solid paste and slurry. Following, halophyte juice slurry was used as media for the enzymatic hydrolysis of pretreated halophyte fibers.

For enzymatic hydrolysis, Cellic® CTec3 (Novozymes A/S) was used as a source of cellulases and hemicellulases, with a specific enzymatic activity of 214 FPU/mL and a density of 1.2 g/mL. The pretreated *S. ramosissima* lignocellulose was dried at 60°C until completely dry and then ground into a fine powder using the GRINDOMIX GM 200 (Retsch GmbH, Germany). The enzymatic hydrolysis mixture, with a total weight of 500 g, consisted of 50 g of dried and ground *S. ramosissima* lignocellulose fibers, 5.6 g of enzymatic solution (equivalent to 4.67 mL and 20 FPU/g of lignocellulose biomass on dry matter basis), and 442 g of *S. ramosissima* juice slurry. These components were combined in 1 L shaking flasks using table weights, resulting in a final dry matter loading of 10 % (w/w). The flasks were incubated at 50°C and 170 RPM for 24 h. After incubation, unhydrolyzed solids were removed by centrifugation (SL 16 Centrifuge, Thermo Fisher Scientific) at 4500 RPM for 10 min. The sugar-rich hydrolysate slurry was then used for microbial cultivation, composition analysis, and the remaining sample was stored at -20°C . The composition of *S. ramosissima* straw and juice used to produce the hydrolysate is presented in Table 1. For context, a comparison with representative values for other halophyte species as well as conventional plant biomasses and juices is also included. Based on this comparison, it is evident that *S. ramosissima* biomass is particularly distinguished by its exceptionally high ash content, especially in the juice fraction (55 % DM), which is significantly greater than that of typical terrestrial plant juices such as clover, alfalfa, or fruit juices. This reflects the naturally high mineral and salt load of halophytes, a trait rarely encountered in conventional lignocellulosic or green juice substrates. This unique matrix, with its high mineral load and distinctive composition, can strongly influence microbial growth, stress tolerance, and metabolic activity during fermentation processes. Moreover, in comparison with other plant juices, halophyte juice contains relatively low levels of free sugars, limiting the availability of fermentable carbohydrates. As a result, additional carbon sources are often required to support efficient fermentation.

2.2. Microorganisms and inoculum

The bacterial and yeast strains used in this study were *Bacillus coagulans* ATCC 7050, *Lactobacillus plantarum* DSM 13272, *Kluyveromyces marxianus* DSM 7238, *Kluyveromyces marxianus* DSM 70292, *Cyberlindnera jadinii* DSM 70163, *Cyberlindnera jadinii* DSM 2361, *Yarrowia lipolytica* DSM 8218, and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (commercial dry yeast, Maltaserkors tørgær, De Danske Spritfabrikker A/S, Denmark). Bacterial strains were stored on MRS (De Man–Rogosa–Sharpe) agar at 4°C . For inoculum preparation, the bacterial cultures were then transferred to liquid MRS broth and incubated for 24 h at 37°C and 150 RPM. The *K. marxianus* strains, *C. jadinii* strains, *Y. lipolytica* DSM 8218 were stored on YPD (Yeast Extract Peptone Dextrose) agar at 4°C and for

Table 1

The composition of *S. ramosissima* fibers and juice used in the present study, with approximate comparison to halophyte species and other common plant biomass and juice. Values expressed as g/100 g dry matter (DM). "n.d." indicates no data available.

Biomass	Total sugars (g/100 g DM)	Crude protein (g/100 g DM)	Lignin (g/100 g DM)	Ash (g/100 g DM)	Free sugars (g/100 g DM)	Reference
<i>Chemical composition of plant straw and lignocellulosic residues</i>						
<i>S. ramosissima</i> straw	47.1 ± 3.4	5.5 ± 0.3	19.0 ± 0.1	20.9 ± 1.2	n.d.	Present work
Approximate composition of halophyte straw	12–67	15–30	4–28	5–56	n.d.	(Abideen et al., 2011; Attia-Ismail, 2008; Hulkko et al., 2022b)
Corn stover	28–73	4–8	11–23	4–10	n.d.	(Karunanithy and Muthukumarappan, 2010; Wang et al., 2021)
Wheat straw	57–60	2–4	16–18	7–16	n.d.	(Panagiotopoulos et al., 2013; Passoth and Sandgren, 2019; Petersen et al., 2009)
Sugarcane bagasse	52–80	1–3	10–30	1–16	n.d.	(de Rocha et al., 2015; Shabbirahmed et al., 2022)
Switchgrass	49–72	5–14	16–30	1–8	n.d.	(Giannoulis et al., 2022; Larnaudie et al., 2022)
<i>Chemical composition of plant juice</i>						
<i>S. ramosissima</i> juice	9.6 ± 0.1	11.5 ± 0.9	10.9 ± 0.1	54.5 ± 3.7	3.8 ± 0.1	Present work
Approximate composition of halophyte juice	10–35	8–34	5–10	45–76	1–2	(Alassali et al., 2017; Cayenne et al., 2022; Hulkko et al., 2022b)
Clover juice	20–25	22–38	9–14	10–16	10–20	(Guo et al., 2022; Pap et al., 2024; Santamaria-Fernández et al., 2019)
Alfalfa juice	10–20	37–50	0–2	10–12	8–15	(Coburn et al., 2021; Gaffey et al., 2023; Koegel et al., 1999)
Apple pomace juice	80–90	1	2–10	1–3	80–90	(Markowski et al., 2009; Persic et al., 2017; Wu and Siebert, 2002)
Sugarcane juice	86–95	2–6	1–3	1–4	84–93	(Arif et al., 2019; Medeiros et al., 2017)
Sweet sorghum juice	90–97	1–4	n.d.	2–6	90–97	(Eggleston et al., 2022; Hu et al., 2022)

inoculum preparation they were grown in YPD broth for 24 h at 32 °C and 150 RPM, except for *K. marxianus* strains, which were grown at 37 °C. *S. cerevisiae* was used as freeze-dried and did not require pre-inoculation before cultivation on hydrolysate.

2.3. Microbial cultivation on halophyte-based media

For yeast cultivation on halophyte-based hydrolysate, 90 mL of hydrolysate slurry was added to a 250 mL Erlenmeyer flask, followed by 10 mL of yeast inoculum grown in YPD broth. For *S. cerevisiae*, instead of liquid inoculum, 0.2 g of freeze-dried cells was added to 100 mL of hydrolysate. The samples were incubated at 32 °C and 150 RPM for 72 h, except for *K. marxianus* strains, which were incubated at 37 °C.

For bacterial and yeast co-cultures on halophyte-based hydrolysate, 90 mL of hydrolysate slurry was added to a 250 mL Erlenmeyer flask, followed by 5 mL of yeast inoculum grown in YPD broth, and 5 mL of bacterial inoculum grown in MRS broth. In the case of *S. cerevisiae* and bacterial co-cultures, instead of liquid yeast inoculum, 0.1 g of freeze-dried cells was added to 95 mL of hydrolysate, along with 5 mL of bacterial inoculum from MRS broth.

Additionally, control samples containing only hydrolysate were incubated to assess the growth of naturally present microorganisms in the *S. ramosissima* biomass. All cultivations were conducted under aerobic conditions, with flasks sealed using caps equipped with PTFE

Table 2

Combinations of bacteria and yeast used in co-culture trials, along with the incubation temperatures for each microbial combination and control samples.

Bacterial culture	Yeast culture	Temperature °C
<i>B. coagulans</i> ATCC 7050	<i>K. marxianus</i> DSM 7238	37
<i>B. coagulans</i> ATCC 7050	<i>K. marxianus</i> DSM 70292	37
<i>B. coagulans</i> ATCC 7050	<i>C. jadinii</i> DSM 2361	32
<i>B. coagulans</i> ATCC 7050	<i>C. jadinii</i> DSM 70163	32
<i>B. coagulans</i> ATCC 7050	<i>S. cerevisiae</i>	32
<i>L. plantarum</i> DSM 13272	<i>K. marxianus</i> DSM 7238	37
<i>L. plantarum</i> DSM 13272	<i>K. marxianus</i> DSM 70292	37
<i>L. plantarum</i> DSM 13272	<i>C. jadinii</i> DSM 2361	32
<i>L. plantarum</i> DSM 13272	<i>C. jadinii</i> DSM 70163	32
<i>L. plantarum</i> DSM 13272	<i>S. cerevisiae</i>	32
Control		32/37

membranes to allow gas exchange. The samples used in co-cultivation are presented in Table 2.

After incubation, the broths were transferred into two 50 mL Falcon tubes, with one stored at –20 °C. The samples were then centrifuged (SL 16 Centrifuge, Thermo Fisher Scientific) at 3000 RPM for 10 min. The supernatants were collected in 50 mL Falcon tubes, while the cell pellets were washed with 30 mL of Milli-Q water and centrifuged again. This washing process was repeated twice. The washed cells were stored at –80 °C overnight, then freeze-dried for three days and used to determine biomass production and crude protein concentration in the broths. Five mL of the collected supernatant was carefully pipetted into new 50 mL Falcon tubes and diluted with 20 mL of Milli-Q water. The diluted hydrolysates were then filtered using 0.22 µm syringe filters and transferred into HPLC vials for sugar content analysis. For long-term storage, the HPLC vials containing hydrolysates were kept at –20 °C.

2.4. Optimization of inoculum size and cultivation time of selected co-cultures

For the optimization of inoculum size and cultivation time, *B. coagulans* ATCC 7050 was used as the bacterial culture, while *Kluyveromyces marxianus* DSM 7238, *C. jadinii* DSM 70163, *C. jadinii* DSM 2361, and *S. cerevisiae* were used as yeast cultures, making a total of four co-culture combinations. For this trial, *S. cerevisiae* was pre-cultivated on YPD medium and inoculated in the same manner as the other yeast strains. The experimental design is shown in Table 3. This full

Table 3

The experimental design for inoculum size and cultivation time optimization.

Cultivation time (hours)	Inoculation size yeast (%) (v/v)	Inoculation size bacteria (%) (v/v)
24	1	1
24	10	10
72	1	1
72	10	10
48	5	5
48	5	5
48	5	5
48	5	5
48	5	5

factorial experiment was conducted with one trial at each level, and five replicates for the central points to assess variability. Cultivation was carried out in 250 mL Erlenmeyer flasks with a total volume of 100 mL, where the amount of hydrolysate was adjusted based on the inoculum size, as detailed in Table 3. The samples were incubated at 32 °C or 37 °C, with shaking at 150 RPM. After cultivation, the samples were processed as described in subchapter 2.3.

2.5. Dry matter, crude protein, free sugars, organic acids, and vitamin B12 analysis

The dry matter (DM) was determined in samples based on the analytical method developed by the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) (Sluiter et al., 2008). The pH of liquid samples was analyzed by a pH meter (913 pH Meter, Metrohm).

A CHNS elemental analyzer (Pekin Elmer 2400 series CHNS/O) was used to analyze the total nitrogen content in samples. A 2–10 mg of dried sample was weighed in a small tin capsule and analyzed with the elemental analyzer.

The crude protein content was calculated based on the nitrogen content, by using a nitrogen-to-protein conversion factor (NPCF) of 6.25 (Mariotti et al., 2008). The number, taken from the literature, is not an exact figure, but represents a well-accepted, widely used approximation. Eq. (1) used for the nitrogen-to-protein conversion is:

$$CP = N \times NPCF \quad (1)$$

where N is nitrogen content % (w/w) in the dried sample, NPCF is the mass ratio of nitrogen to protein, 6.25, and CP is a crude protein content % (w/w) in the dried sample. Mass balances for cell dry weight and crude protein content were calculated as described in (Santamaría-Fernández et al., 2017). Free sugars were analyzed through HPLC (1260 Infinity II, Agilent Technologies). The characterization of sugars and organic acids in hydrolysate and broths was based on the analytical protocol by NREL (Sluiter et al., 2006). Prior to HPLC analysis, samples were filtered through 0.22 µm syringe filters into HPLC vials. Sugars (glucose, xylose, and arabinose), ethanol, and acetic acid were analyzed using an HPLC system equipped with a Bio-Rad Aminex HPX-87H column (Bio-Rad Laboratories Inc.), employing a 0.005 M H₂SO₄ mobile phase and a refractive index detector (RID). Lactic acid analysis was conducted on the same system but utilized a 0.2 % (v/v) H₃PO₄ mobile phase with diode array detection (DAD). Vitamin B12 was quantified via HPLC using an Agilent Poroshell 120 EC-C18 column (4.6 × 100 mm, 2.7 µm) with eluants A) 90 % (v/v) MeOH in Milli-Q water (30 %) and B) Milli-Q water with 0.6 % TFA (70 %), analyzed with DAD. The applied method measures vitamin B12 and related corrinoid compounds with similar structures; therefore, results may represent both true vitamin B12 and B12-like compounds present in the samples.

2.6. Statistical methods

All trials were performed as triplicates, and the samples were prepared in random order. All results are given as mean values with standard deviation. The ANOVA test was used for the analysis of experimental results with single or multiple independent variables. The significance level was set to 0.05 for all performed statistical tests. When necessary, ANOVA was supplemented by Tukey's Honest Significant Difference (HSD) test.

Second-order Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) was performed for the analysis of optimization experiments with inoculum size and cultivation time, based on response surface methodology. The MLR outcomes are presented graphically in the form of 2D contour plots, showing the dependence of response (dependent variable), including cell dry weight and crude protein concentration, on the factors under optimization (independent variables), involving inoculum size and cultivation time.

The correlation analysis was performed to investigate linear

association between all factors. The Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) was used to quantify these associations, with $r \geq 0.7$ indicating strong correlation between variables. To further explore patterns and relationships within the dataset, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was employed as an exploratory method. PCA reduces high-dimensional data by transforming the original variable space into a smaller set of latent variables, known as principal components (PCs), which capture the directions of maximum variance in the data. The results of PCA are presented through scores and loadings plots. The scores plot visualizes how individual data points project onto a new coordinate system defined by the principal components, typically using the first two components (PC1 and PC2). The loadings plot illustrates the contribution of each original variable to the principal components, and reveals correlations among variables. Each principal component is characterized by its explained variance, which represents the proportion of the total variance retained in the lower-dimensional space. This approach aids in identifying underlying data structures, while enhancing visualization and interpretation.

R version 4.3.1 (R Core Team, 2020), with RStudio software (v. 2024.09.0 Build 375), was used for all statistical analyses. For correlation visualization and PCA, R was supplemented with *corrplot* package (v. 0.95) (Wei et al., 2024), and *mdatools* package (v. 0.14.2) (Kucheryavskiy, 2020).

3. Results

3.1. Yeast cultivation on halophyte-based media

As an initial investigation, halophyte-based hydrolysate was used as a cultivation medium for selected yeast strains to assess its stability as a substrate for single-culture growth. Based on the results shown in Fig. 1, *K. marxianus* DSM 70292, *C. jadinii* DSM 70163, and *Y. lipolytica* DSM 8218 did not consume free sugars present in the hydrolysate. However, variations in organic acid levels suggest some utilization of these compounds. Additionally, the higher cell dry weight content compared to the hydrolysate indicates that other carbon sources were likely utilized by these strains.

In contrast, *K. marxianus* DSM 7238 and *C. jadinii* DSM 2361 demonstrated excellent utilization of free sugars, except for xylose in *C. jadinii* DSM 2361. Ethanol production was observed in both strains, suggesting a possible oxidofermentative metabolism, despite aerobic cultivation conditions. This could be due to an inhibitory environment in the hydrolysate or the Crabtree effect. Nevertheless, both strains achieved comparable dried cell concentrations of 9.6 g/L and 10.0 g/L, respectively. Another well-performing strain was *S. cerevisiae*, which was able to utilize the majority of available carbon sources. However, since *S. cerevisiae* can only metabolize C6 sugars, it is possible that inherent microorganisms present in the halophyte juice co-grew with the yeast. The achieved cell dry weight was 10 g/L, similar to *K. marxianus* DSM 7238 and *C. jadinii* DSM 2361.

The statistical analysis showed that yeast cultivation had a significant impact on hydrolysate composition. The one-way ANOVA confirmed that yeast cultivation was statistically significant for total sugar (F-value = 314, p-value < 0.0001, $\eta^2 = 0.996$), glucose (F-value = 271, p-value < 0.0001, $\eta^2 = 0.995$), xylose (F-value = 115, p-value < 0.0001, $\eta^2 = 0.99$), arabinose (F-value = 75.3, p-value < 0.0001, $\eta^2 = 0.985$), ethanol (F-value = 6.29, p-value = 0.0145, $\eta^2 = 0.843$), and cell dry weight (CDW) (F-value = 17.8, p-value = 0.0007, $\eta^2 = 0.938$). However, there was no statistically significant difference in acetic and lactic acid content between hydrolysate and culture samples, except for *S. cerevisiae* and *C. jadinii*, which showed significant differences compared to the hydrolysate. Furthermore, the Tukey HSD test confirmed that samples cultivated with *S. cerevisiae*, *K. marxianus* DSM 7238, and *C. jadinii* DSM 2361 achieved the highest CDW, with no statistically significant differences among them. This supports these three strains as potential candidates for yeast cell and postbiotic production.

Fig. 1. Composition of halophyte-based hydrolysate and broths after cultivation with selected yeast strains: A) glucose, xylose, arabinose; B) acetic acid, lactic acid and ethanol; C) cell dry weight (CDW). “★” indicates statistical significance compared to hydrolysate (control).

3.2. Screening of co-cultivation of LAB and yeast

Based on the results from Section 3.1, *Y. lipolytica* DSM 8218 was excluded from further investigation due to its poor performance compared to other yeast strains. In contrast, *K. marxianus* DSM 70292 and *C. jadinii* DSM 70163, despite showing no consumption of free sugars in the hydrolysate and exhibiting lower growth, were retained for subsequent screening. This decision was based on previous studies showing that these species, in general, perform strongly in mixed cultures with bacteria and possess excellent potential for postbiotic production and promising probiotic traits, even though these specific strains had not been tested under such conditions before.

As shown in Fig. 2, there was no considerable sugar consumption or production of organic acids and ethanol in the control samples, indicating minimal or no growth of contaminant microorganisms. However, a small amount of precipitate containing protein was observed. This may be attributed to residual biomass from the hydrolysate that was not completely removed during solids separation or that precipitated during cultivation. Moreover, the protein levels in the control samples were significantly lower than in the cultivated samples, confirming that cultivation led to cell growth and protein production. When comparing

L. plantarum DSM 13272 and *B. coagulans* ATCC 7050, the primary difference was in lactic acid content. Lactic acid was not detected in samples with *B. coagulans* ATCC 7050, suggesting that its production rate was lower compared to *L. plantarum* DSM 13272, or that yeast utilized the lactic acid. Alternatively, the absence of lactic acid may indicate that *B. coagulans* ATCC 7050 did not grow effectively or not at all. However, the consumption of xylose and arabinose in the co-culture combination based on *B. coagulans* ATCC 7050 and *S. cerevisiae* suggests that bacterial growth occurred, as the yeast was only able to utilize C6 sugars.

Overall, yeast cultivated with *B. coagulans* ATCC 7050 performed better in terms of cell dry weight and crude protein content compared to those grown with *L. plantarum* DSM 13272. This may be due to lactic acid accumulation inhibiting growth at higher concentrations or to *L. plantarum* DSM 13272 growing more rapidly, thereby limiting yeast growth. However, free sugar was detected in most samples containing *L. plantarum* DSM 13272, suggesting that competition for C-sources was unlikely to be the limiting factor. The highest cell production was observed with *S. cerevisiae*, *K. marxianus* DSM 7238, and *C. jadinii* DSM 2361 in combination with *B. coagulans* ATCC 7050, achieving cell dry weights of 9.6, 10.6, and 10.2 g/L of broth, respectively, with crude protein concentrations of 4.5, 3.2, and 4.8 g/L. These results align with the findings from Section 3.1 on yeast-only cultivation, supporting the validity of the observed patterns. Additionally, ethanol and formic acid were analyzed but were not detected in any of the samples. Because fermentations were performed under non-sterile conditions, some contribution from indigenous microorganisms in the halophyte hydrolysate cannot be fully excluded. Nonetheless, control samples without inoculum exhibited negligible sugar depletion or product formation, and the high salinity and antimicrobial metabolites of *S. ramosissima* are expected to suppress most background microbiota. These factors suggest that the inoculated strains were the predominant drivers of the observed fermentation performance.

Furthermore, vitamin B12 levels, antioxidant capacity, and TPC were analyzed, as shown in Table 4. The results indicate that the control samples exhibited some B12 production, suggesting the growth of naturally occurring microorganisms in the halophyte biomass. Additionally, a significant difference in B12 production was observed between samples containing *B. coagulans* ATCC 7050 and *L. plantarum* DSM 13272, indicating that *B. coagulans* ATCC 7050 contributes substantially to vitamin B12 synthesis. Reported concentrations represent total vitamin B12 and structurally related corrinoid compounds detected by the applied HPLC DAD method. While the majority of production is attributed to the inoculated strains, contributions from naturally occurring microorganisms present in the non-sterile hydrolysate cannot be excluded. The observed pattern, with peak values in *B. coagulans*-containing fermentations, is consistent with the known ability of *B. coagulans* to synthesize vitamin B12 (García et al., 2024; Kallur et al., 2022; Liang et al., 2024).

Regarding antioxidant capacity, the reduction levels were relatively low across all samples. To be considered a strong antioxidant agent, the reduction should exceed 80 %. However, certain co-cultures, such as *S. cerevisiae* with *B. coagulans* ATCC 7050, demonstrated an increase in antioxidant capacity. For TPC, no significant differences were observed between the hydrolysate and fermented broth, suggesting minimal interaction between phenolics in the plant material and the bacterial or yeast strains. However, an increase in TPC between the raw juice and hydrolysate suggests that pretreatment has a considerable effect on phenolic release. This can be attributed to the impact of pretreatment on halophyte lignocellulose, which facilitates the breakdown of the lignin fraction, thereby releasing phenolics into the hydrolysate.

The *N*-way ANOVA, shown in Table 5, was supplemented with a Tukey HSD test showed that *L. plantarum* DSM 13272 and *B. coagulans* ATCC 7050 exhibited significantly different effects on sugar consumption, vitamin B12 production, acetic acid, and lactic acid levels. Notably, the bacterial strain contributed significantly to the variance in B12 and lactic acid concentrations, aligning with the known metabolic roles of

Fig. 2. Composition of halophyte-based hydrolysate, control samples incubated at 32 °C and 37 °C, and broths after co-cultivation with bacterial and yeast strains: A) glucose, xylose, arabinose; B) acetic acid and lactic acid; C) cell dry weight and crude protein. “*” indicates statistically significant differences for each yeast–bacteria combination compared to the hydrolysate and control samples.

lactic acid bacteria and *Bacillus* species in organic acid and corrinoid metabolism. In contrast, they had little to no effect on crude protein production and cell dry weight. While bacteria alone had no effect on certain parameters, their interaction with yeast was significant for all measured variables, except for acetic acid. On the other hand, it seems that yeast cultures were the main drivers of cell and protein formation. Furthermore, it was confirmed that type of yeast strain generally did have an overall significant impact on cell dry weight, crude protein content, sugar consumption, except in the case of *K. marxianus* DSM 70292. This strain exhibited the lowest cell dry weight, crude protein production, sugar and organic acid consumption compared to other yeast strains. Moreover, it was confirmed *C. jadinii* strains demonstrated highest organic acid utilization, especially acetic acid, compared to other strains. Based on the results, the most promising bacteria-yeast

combinations include *K. marxianus* DSM 7238, *C. jadinii* DSM 2361, *C. jadinii* DSM 70163, and *S. cerevisiae*, with *B. coagulans* ATCC 7050 as the optimal bacterial strain.

3.3. Optimization of inoculation size and time of selected co-cultures

Based on the outcomes presented in section 3.2, the decision was reached to conduct a more in-depth study into the effect of inoculum size and cultivation time on cell dry mass and protein production by selected co-culture based on the combination of *B. coagulans* ATCC 7050 with one of these yeasts *K. marxianus* DSM 7238, *C. jadinii* DSM 2361, *C. jadinii* DSM 70163, and *S. cerevisiae*. The hydrolysate used in the experiment contained 0.91 ± 0.05 g/L of lactic acid, 0.95 ± 0.01 g/L of acetic acid, a pH of 4.65, and 16.1 ± 0.3 g/L of free sugars.

Table 4

Content of B12, Antioxidant capacity, TPC in the raw juice, hydrolysate, control samples and, co-cultivated samples. "n.d." indicates that the compound was either absent or present below the method's measurable threshold in the corresponding sample.

Sample/Bacterial culture	Yeast culture	B12 (mg/L)	Antioxidant capacity (%)	TPC (g/L)
<i>S. ramosissima</i> juice		n.d.	16.8 ± 0.6	3.6 ± 0.2
Hydrolysate		n.d.	28.2 ± 0.6	13.8 ± 1.2
Control 32°C		0.38 ± 0.02	26.9 ± 1.3	13.2 ± 0.5
Control 37°C		0.44 ± 0.001	28.7 ± 5.0	13.0 ± 0.3
<i>B. coagulans</i> ATCC 7050	<i>K. marxianus</i> DSM 7238	3.13 ± 0.01	34.2 ± 3.3	13.3 ± 1.0
<i>B. coagulans</i> ATCC 7050	<i>K. marxianus</i> DSM 70292	5.60 ± 0.29	33.5 ± 5.9	13.4 ± 0.9
<i>B. coagulans</i> ATCC 7050	<i>C. jadinii</i> DSM 2361	0.65 ± 0.14	39.3 ± 7.6	12.7 ± 0.1
<i>B. coagulans</i> ATCC 7050	<i>C. jadinii</i> DSM 70163	41.4 ± 0.9	41.0 ± 4.6	13.0 ± 0.1
<i>B. coagulans</i> ATCC 7050	<i>S. cerevisiae</i>	4.42 ± 2.70	54.9 ± 6.1	13.7 ± 0.6
<i>L. plantarum</i> DSM 13272	<i>K. marxianus</i> DSM 7238	n.d.	39.9 ± 6.8	11.9 ± 0.1
<i>L. plantarum</i> DSM 13272	<i>K. marxianus</i> DSM 70292	n.d.	23.4 ± 0.3	14.3 ± 0.2
<i>L. plantarum</i> DSM 13272	<i>C. jadinii</i> DSM 2361	4.10 ± 0.19	23.4 ± 0.4	13.0 ± 0.3
<i>L. plantarum</i> DSM 13272	<i>C. jadinii</i> DSM 70163	n.d.	26.4 ± 2.5	13.6 ± 0.9
<i>L. plantarum</i> DSM 13272	<i>S. cerevisiae</i>	n.d.	21.1 ± 1.0	12.8 ± 0.1

Table 5

N-way ANOVA with bacteria, yeast and their combined effect as influencing factors on the investigated variables.

Effect of co-cultures on cell dry weight	F-value	p-value	η^2
Bacteria	6.67	0.027	0.033
Yeast	37.4	5.48×10^{-6}	0.745
Bacteria:Yeast	8.68	0.002	0.173
Effect of co-cultures on crude protein content			
Bacteria	27.8	0.0004	0.062
Yeast	88.0	9.43×10^{-8}	0.789
Bacteria:Yeast	14.0	0.0004	0.126
Effect of co-cultures on lactic acid			
Bacteria	6603	1.95×10^{-15}	0.460
Yeast	969	6.75×10^{-13}	0.270
Bacteria:Yeast	969	6.75×10^{-13}	0.270
Effect of co-cultures on acetic acid			
Bacteria	6.76	0.03	0.020
Yeast	75.2	2.01×10^{-7}	0.908
Bacteria:Yeast	3.49	0.05	0.042
Effect of co-cultures on B12			
Bacteria	1326	5.78×10^{-12}	0.460
Yeast	183	2.63×10^{-9}	0.254
Bacteria:Yeast	203	1.58×10^{-9}	0.282
Effect of co-cultures on sugar consumption			
Bacteria	1374	4.87×10^{-12}	0.080
Yeast	3403	1.28×10^{-15}	0.798
Bacteria:Yeast	518	1.53×10^{-11}	0.121

The N-way ANOVA results indicated that inoculum size and cultivation time had a statistically significant impact on CDW and crude protein production across all co-cultures. More specifically, in co-culture with *C. jadinii* DSM 2361, cultivation time had a stronger impact on CDW ($F = 52.2$, $p = 0.0019$, $\eta^2 = 0.663$), while inoculum size had a more modest effect ($F = 9.74$, $p = 0.0355$, $\eta^2 = 0.124$). Crude protein content in the same culture was strongly influenced by both cultivation time ($F = 31.8$, $p = 0.0049$, $\eta^2 = 0.398$) and inoculum size ($F = 36.1$, $p = 0.0039$, $\eta^2 = 0.452$). In the case of *C. jadinii* DSM 70163, both CDW and crude protein production were influenced by cultivation time (CDW: $F = 10.5$, $p = 0.0316$, $\eta^2 = 0.335$; crude protein: $F = 6.56$, $p = 0.0626$, $\eta^2 = 0.231$), with inoculum size exerting an even greater influence on both parameters (CDW: $F = 14.4$, $p = 0.0192$, $\eta^2 = 0.459$; crude protein: $F = 15.7$, $p = 0.0166$, $\eta^2 = 0.554$). For *S. cerevisiae*, CDW was significantly affected by both cultivation time ($F = 22.1$, $p = 0.0069$, $\eta^2 = 0.582$) and inoculum size ($F = 27.51$, $p = 0.0063$, $\eta^2 = 0.362$). Similarly, crude protein production was strongly influenced by cultivation time ($F = 55.3$, $p = 0.0018$, $\eta^2 = 0.651$), and to a lesser extent by inoculum size ($F = 21.7$, $p = 0.0096$, $\eta^2 = 0.256$). Finally, *K. marxianus* DSM 7238 showed a similar pattern, with CDW influenced predominantly by time ($F = 30.9$, $p = 0.0037$, $\eta^2 = 0.648$), and to a lesser degree by inoculum size ($F = 13.3$, $p = 0.0218$, $\eta^2 = 0.140$). Crude protein content in this culture was also significantly affected by both time ($F = 129$, $p = 0.0003$, $\eta^2 = 0.476$) and inoculum size ($F = 96.5$, $p = 0.0006$, $\eta^2 = 0.355$).

Moreover, MLR analysis was conducted for each co-culture to further examine the effects of inoculum size and cultivation time on cell dry mass and crude protein production, with the results visualized as contour plots in Fig. 3. The generated models explain a significant portion of the variability in product concentrations, with an adjusted R^2 ranging from 0.71 to 0.97.

For individual microbial combinations, *C. jadinii* DSM 2361 exhibited a quadratic effect, as shown in Fig. 3A and B. The negative coefficients for the quadratic terms (-1.94 for cell dry mass concentration and -0.74 for crude protein production) in MLR model suggest that while increasing cultivation time initially enhances production, excessive durations lead to a decline. This decline is likely due to resource depletion, accumulation of metabolic byproducts, or other environmental limitations. Based on these findings, the optimal cultivation time for *C. jadinii* DSM 2361 appears to be between 2.5 and 3 days post-inoculation.

For other microbial combinations, the relationship between inoculum size, cultivation time, and products was more linear, meaning that higher inoculum sizes and longer cultivation times generally resulted in increased cell and crude protein yields, with the optimal cultivation time extending beyond 72 h, as shown in Fig. 3C–H. Notably, the highest product concentrations were observed in co-cultures of *B. coagulans* ATCC 7050 with *K. marxianus* DSM 7238 and *S. cerevisiae*, achieving 17.5 g of CDW and 6.9 g of crude protein/L of broth and 16.5 g of CDW and 6.3 g of crude protein/L of broth, respectively. These maximum yields were attained at the highest inoculum level 10 (v/v %) after the longest cultivation time point of 72 h.

Moreover, samples were analyzed for pH, B12, remaining free sugars, lactic acid, and acetic acid, with the results presented in Table 6. The decreasing concentrations of acetic and lactic acids across all samples, combined with a steady increase in pH over the cultivation period, suggest that the yeasts present are actively consuming these acids. This indicates their potential for effective deacidification in mixed microbial cultures. For example, in the *K. marxianus* DSM 7238 co-culture, pH increased significantly from 5.13 to 8.41. This rise may be attributed to yeast metabolism shifting towards amino acid consumption once the primary carbon source is depleted, leading to ammonia release and a subsequent pH increase. Overall, a larger inoculum size of 10 (v/v %) resulted in higher sugar consumption, greater organic acid utilization, and a more pronounced pH increase compared to lower inoculum sizes. Notably, after just 24 h of cultivation, most free sugars were depleted,

(caption on next page)

Fig. 3. Contour plots based on MLR analysis with inoculum size and time of cultivation as selected variables and cell dry weight and crude protein/L of broth as response factors for selected microbial combinations. A) Effect of inoculum size and time of cultivation on cell dry weight/L of broth with *B. coagulans* ATCC 7050 and *C. jadinii* DSM 2361 co-culture (F-value of 19.8 and R^2 of 0.90); B) Effect of inoculum size and time of cultivation on crude protein/L of broth with *B. coagulans* ATCC 7050 and *C. jadinii* DSM 2361 co-culture (F-value of 20.6 and R^2 of 0.95); C) Effect of inoculum size and time of cultivation on cell dry weight/L of broth with *B. coagulans* ATCC 7050 and *C. jadinii* DSM 70163 co-culture (F-value of 7.1 and R^2 of 0.75); D) Effect of inoculum size and time of cultivation on crude protein/L of broth with *B. coagulans* ATCC 7050 and *C. jadinii* DSM 70163 co-culture (F-value of 6.0 and R^2 of 0.71); E) Effect of inoculum size and time of cultivation on cell dry weight/L of broth with *B. coagulans* ATCC 7050 and *K. marxianus* DSM 7238 co-culture (F-value of 22.0 and R^2 of 0.96); F) Effect of inoculum size and time of cultivation on crude protein/L of broth with *B. coagulans* ATCC 7050 and *K. marxianus* DSM 7238 co-culture (F-value of 68.3 and R^2 of 0.97); G) Effect of inoculum size and time of cultivation on cell dry weight/L of broth with *B. coagulans* ATCC 7050 and *S. cerevisiae* co-culture (F-value of 18.3 and R^2 of 0.90); H) Effect of inoculum size and time of cultivation on crude protein/L of broth with *B. coagulans* ATCC 7050 and *S. cerevisiae* co-culture (F-value of 20.2 and R^2 of 0.91).

Table 6

Measured levels of remaining free sugars, lactic acid, acetic acid, and vitamin B12 in the broths after cultivation at various time points and inoculum sizes, following a full factorial experimental design with selected microbial co-cultures. "n.d." indicates that the compound was either absent or present below the method's measurable threshold in the corresponding sample.

<i>B. coagulans</i> ATCC 7050 and <i>C. jadinii</i> DSM 2361						
Cultivation time (hours)	Inoculation size bacteria and yeast (%) (v/v)	Remaining free sugars (g/L)	B12 (mg/L)	Lactic acid (g/L)	Acetic acid (g/L)	pH
24	1	5.33	2.30	0.28	0.41	4.67
24	10	3.57	6.98	0.08	0.44	5.54
48	5	1.98 ± 0.79	25.3 ± 1.6	0.06 ± 0.04	0.05 ± 0.04	5.59 ± 0.20
72	1	0.95	24.7	0.21	n.d.	5.69
72	10	1.20	20.1	0.13	n.d.	6.80
<i>B. coagulans</i> ATCC 7050 and <i>C. jadinii</i> DSM 70163						
Cultivation time (hours)	Inoculation size bacteria and yeast (%) (v/v)	Remaining free sugars (g/L)	B12 (mg/L)	Lactic acid (g/L)	Acetic acid (g/L)	pH
24	1	3.77	n.d.	0.765	0.29	4.84
24	10	2.32	2.95	n.d.	0.06	5.94
48	5	1.66 ± 0.20	27.8 ± 2.5	0.40 ± 0.06	0.09 ± 0.04	5.62 ± 0.42
72	1	1.63	25.7	n.d.	n.d.	5.88
72	10	0.20	25.1	n.d.	n.d.	7.60
<i>B. coagulans</i> ATCC 7050 and <i>K. marxianus</i> DSM 7238						
Cultivation time (hours)	Inoculation size bacteria and yeast (%) (v/v)	Remaining free sugars (g/L)	B12 (mg/L)	Lactic acid (g/L)	Acetic acid (g/L)	pH
24	1	2.11	19.9	0.15	1.65	4.76
24	10	1.19	9.56	0.07	1.92	5.13
48	5	0.57 ± 0.12	26.0 ± 11.1	0.09 ± 0.05	1.52 ± 0.09	5.41 ± 0.14
72	1	n.d.	42.2	n.d.	n.d.	6.66
72	10	0.08	n.d.	0.22	n.d.	8.41
<i>B. coagulans</i> ATCC 7050 and <i>S. cerevisiae</i>						
Cultivation time (hours)	Inoculation size bacteria and yeast (%) (v/v)	Remaining free sugars (g/L)	B12 (mg/L)	Lactic acid (g/L)	Acetic acid (g/L)	pH
24	1	3.01	5.90	0.03	0.29	5.58
24	10	2.75	6.63	0.11	0.55	5.84
48	5	0.17 ± 0.06	12.1 ± 1.2	0.19 ± 0.02	n.d.	5.86 ± 0.11
72	1	0.17	14.0	0.18	n.d.	6.54
72	10	n.d.	47.5	0.33	n.d.	7.42

particularly in co-cultures with *K. marxianus* DSM 7238 and *S. cerevisiae*. However, as shown in Fig. 3, cell growth continues beyond 72 h, suggesting that microbial cultures are utilizing alternative nutrient sources. Furthermore, sugar utilization was highest in co-cultures with *K. marxianus* DSM 7238 and *S. cerevisiae*, aligning with the highest observed concentrations of cell dry weight and crude protein production. Similarly, these co-cultures exhibited the highest B12 vitamin production after 72 h of cultivation, reaching 42.2 mg/L with *K. marxianus* DSM 7238 and 47.5 mg/L with *S. cerevisiae*. As in the screening trials, the optimisation experiments were conducted using non-sterile hydrolysate. While low-level activity from naturally occurring microorganisms cannot be entirely excluded, control experiments and the rapid colonisation due to high-density inocula suggest that these background populations contributed minimally to sugar consumption and biomass accumulation. However, they may have played a role in vitamin B12 synthesis. *N*-way ANOVA revealed that cultivation time was generally the most significant factor influencing B12 production, while inoculum size had a limited or inconsistent effect. Specifically, in co-cultures with *S. cerevisiae*, both cultivation time (F-value = 123.37, p-value = 0.0003, η^2 = 0.652) and inoculum size (F-value = 104.72, p-value = 0.0005, η^2 = 0.277) significantly influenced B12 levels. In contrast, for *C. jadinii* DSM 70163, only cultivation time was significant (F-value = 37.31, p-value = 0.0026, η^2 = 0.947), with inoculum size showing no notable effect. A similar pattern was observed for *C. jadinii* DSM 2361, where B12 production was significantly affected by time (F-value = 87.88, p-value = 0.0005, η^2 = 0.956), but not by inoculum size. For *K. marxianus* DSM 7238, neither factor explained the variation in B12 concentration. These results suggest that B12 is produced over time, but not necessarily in direct proportion to inoculum size. This may imply contributions from other factors, such as indigenous microorganisms inherently present in *S. ramosissima* biomass. Another possibility is that *B. coagulans* may produce B12, while the co-inoculated yeast consumes it, resulting in an overall neutral effect of inoculum size on net B12 concentration.

3.4. Correlation and PCA analysis

The correlation analysis, revealed a strong positive relationship between crude protein, cell dry weight (CDW) concentration, and pH. This correlation likely arises from the yeast's ability to deacidify the broth and utilize organic acids and amino acids as nutrient sources. As these compounds are consumed more efficiently, the pH increases. This is a particularly interesting observation, as it suggests that the yeast's capacity for deacidification and organic acid utilization directly influences its growth performance, ultimately positively impacting protein and overall cell mass production. Another group of positively correlated samples formed a cluster consisting of free sugars and organic acids, which showed a negative correlation with protein and CDW concentration. This supports the idea that the overall performance of the co-cultures is driven by the robustness of the yeast and its symbiotic relationship with bacteria. The quality of this interaction appears to enhance the utilization of various carbon sources present in the hydrolysate, contributing to the efficiency of the cultivation process.

The exploratory analysis based on PCA was conducted to confirm patterns and trends observed using correlation analysis and to further

explore interaction between factors. Preliminary investigation of the PCA results showed that PC1 captured 39.5 % of the original data variance, while PC2 captured 13.9 % of the variance; together, PC1 and PC2 explain more than half of the total variance in the dataset. Exploration of higher components (PC3, PC4) did not provide any useful information, and therefore, they have not been incorporated into this article.

Fig. 4 presents the loadings (A) and scores (B) plots for Principal Component 1 (PC1) on the x-axis and Principal Component 2 (PC2) on the y-axis. The loadings plot (Fig. 4A) illustrates the original variables as vectors projected onto the PC1 vs. PC2 space. For clarity, each vector is represented as a point marking the position of its head. The length and direction of these vectors provide insights into the corresponding variables and their relationships. Notably, pH, CDW concentration, and protein concentration are positioned close to each other, indicating a strong positive correlation, consistent with the findings from the correlation heatmap. Conversely, free sugars and organic acids cluster on the opposite side of the plot, highlighting their negative correlation with CDW and protein concentration.

The orientation of the variable vectors in the loadings plot (Fig. 4A) corresponds to the distribution of data points in the scores plot (Fig. 4B), which represents individual co-culture samples in the PC space. The samples are color-coded based on yeast strain. A distinct separation is observed between *K. marxianus* DSM 70292 and the other yeast strains used in samples, confirming its exclusion from optimization trials. Its position in the PC space is farther from CDW and protein concentration than the other strains, supporting the idea for its removal from further investigation. Overall, the remaining yeast strains exhibit a similar relationship with CDW and protein concentration, as the majority of samples are oriented in the same direction.

To further explore the relationships between pH, protein concentration, and CDW concentration, the PC space was color-coded based on these variables, as shown in Fig. 5. The visualization provides a clearer understanding of their interconnections. As evident from the figure, samples with higher pH values also exhibit higher protein and CDW concentrations, reinforcing the correlation observed earlier. Based on these findings, Partial Least Squares (PLS) regression were performed to assess the potential for predicting protein concentration and CDW concentration using pH as a predictor. However, the resulting models yielded unsatisfactory statistical performance, leading to the

abandonment of this approach. Still, given the strong linear correlations and direct interactions observed between these factors, pH could still be considered a useful qualitative control parameter for providing a rough assessment of co-cultivation performance on halophyte-based hydrolysate.

4. Discussion

Initial investigations with six yeast cultures revealed poor nutrient utilization, particularly by *K. marxianus* DSM 70292, *C. jadinii* DSM 70163, and *Y. lipolytica* DSM 8218. In contrast, *K. marxianus* DSM 7238 and *C. jadinii* DSM 2361 demonstrated carbon source utilization but also produced ethanol, which was undesirable in our process. The ethanol production could be explained by the inhibitory nature of the hydrolysate, potentially causing a metabolic shift toward ethanol production even in the presence of oxygen (Rudnyckij et al., 2024). Alternatively, the high sugar concentration may have triggered an oxidofermentative metabolism known as the Crabtree effect (Guo et al., 2025). The best-performing yeast was *S. cerevisiae*, which efficiently consumed most carbon sources. However, the fact that C5 sugars were also utilized suggests that naturally present microorganisms in the halophyte juice may have thrived alongside baker's yeast, as the process was not conducted under sterile conditions. The trial concluded that *S. cerevisiae*, *K. marxianus* DSM 7238, and *C. jadinii* DSM 2361 successfully thrived in the halophyte-based media, while *K. marxianus* DSM 70292, *C. jadinii* DSM 70163, and *Y. lipolytica* DSM 8218 showed limited potential for cultivation in this environment. However, *K. marxianus* DSM 70292 and *C. jadinii* DSM 70163 were still included in the next experiment, as previous research indicated their promising capabilities.

The co-cultivation of selected yeasts with *L. plantarum* DSM 13272 and *B. coagulans* ATCC 7050 demonstrated that overall, co-cultures with *B. coagulans* performed better in terms of cell mass, crude protein, and B12 production. This may be attributed to the fact that *L. plantarum* exhibited better growth compared to *B. coagulans*, leading to elevated lactic acid levels in samples with *L. plantarum*, which in turn inhibited yeast growth. Previous studies have shown that lactic acid and overall organic acids can inhibit yeast growth at certain concentrations (Delmoitié et al., 2025; Narendranath et al., 2001). Notably, statistical analysis revealed that bacterial strains had no significant impact on cell

Fig. 4. A) PCA loadings (map of variables) for PC1 and PC2; B) PCA scores (map of samples) for PC1 vs PC2 colored by yeast strain.

Fig. 5. A) PCA scores (map of samples) for PC1 vs PC2 colored by pH of samples; B) PCA scores (map of samples) for PC1 vs PC2 colored by protein concentration in samples; C) PCA scores (map of samples) for PC1 vs PC2 colored by CDW concentration in samples.

mass or protein production, suggesting that yeast growth is the primary driver of production in bacteria-yeast co-cultures. While the data strongly suggest that the inoculated yeast-bacteria combinations were the primary drivers of fermentation performance, the experiments were conducted under non-sterile conditions, so contributions from naturally occurring microorganisms present in the halophyte hydrolysate cannot be entirely excluded. Several factors indicate that the inoculated strains likely dominated the process: 1) control fermentations without added inoculum exhibited negligible sugar consumption, biomass production, or vitamin B12 formation; 2) the high salinity and mineral content of *S. ramosissima* juice, along with its antimicrobial plant metabolites, are expected to suppress many environmental microorganisms; and 3) the high inoculation rates used favour rapid colonisation by the intended strains. However, based on previous experiment with *S. cerevisiae*, where C5 sugars were consumed, it is likely that other species coexisted in the hydrolysate during cultivation. It is possible that yeast, acting as a natural detoxifier, reduced harmful compounds such as aldehydes (furfural, hydroxymethylfurfural), and phenolics (Jofre et al., 2021), or produced growth factors such as vitamins and amino acids in the hydrolysate (Demirgul et al., 2022), thereby enabling the growth of other microorganisms. Such detoxification and nutrient release could create a more favorable environment, enabling limited growth of other microorganisms without dominating the culture.

The use of non-sterile hydrolysate was intentional, as it reflects industrial conditions where sterilization is not always feasible, and allows evaluation of microbial interactions under realistic settings. In addition to feasibility concerns, sterilization at high temperatures can increase the inhibitory nature of the medium by generating compounds such as furfural and hydroxymethylfurfural (Rudnyckij et al., 2023), which are undesirable, particularly in nutraceutical production, due to their potential toxicity and carcinogenic properties (Meng et al., 2024).

An additional reason for avoiding sterilization lies in the inherent properties of halophytes, which include elevated salt content and antimicrobial plant metabolites, that naturally suppress pathogenic microorganisms (Rudnyckij and Thomsen, 2025). For example, Correia et al. demonstrated that extracts from *Crithmum maritimum* L. not only promoted the growth of probiotic *Lactobacillus bulgaricus* but also exhibited antimicrobial activity against common pathogens such as *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, *Candida albicans*, and *Candida parapsilosis* (Correia et al., 2024). Similarly, halophyte extracts have shown broad antimicrobial potential across various species: essential oils from *Cuminum cyminum*, *C. maritimum*, and *Pimpinella anisum* were effective against *Escherichia coli*, *Listeria monocytogenes*, *S. aureus*, *Pseudomonas fluorescens*, and *C. albicans* (Campana et al., 2022). Extracts of *Salicornia herbacea* inhibited *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (Essaidi

et al., 2013), while *Avicennia marina* displayed strong activity against *C. albicans* and *Bacillus subtilis*, with moderate effects on *Salmonella typhimurium* and *Vibrio damsela* (Yassien et al., 2021). Collectively, these findings underscore the selective antimicrobial potential of halophyte-derived compounds, which can contribute to controlling contamination during fermentation, reducing the necessity for sterilization, and potentially extending product shelf life.

Moreover, similarly to our observations, previous studies align with the benefits of bacteria-yeast co-culturing on alternative feedstocks. For example, Ferreira et al. investigated co-cultures of *L. plantarum* with *Pichia kluyveri*, *Debaryomyces hansenii*, and *Pichia guilliermondii* in a plant-based beverage (Ferreira et al., 2022). Their study demonstrated that co-cultures improved overall survival and metabolic performance compared to *L. plantarum* alone. Moreover, *D. hansenii*, similarly to what was observed in our study, exhibited deacidification during cultivation, further supporting the role of yeast in improving cultivation conditions. The co-culture of *B. coagulans* and *C. jadinii* considerably improved nutrient uptake and microbial growth compared to individual cultures, resulting in approximately 17 g of crude protein/L of *Lactobacilli* wastewater (Liu et al., 2019). In another study, co-cultivation of *Aspergillus niger*, *C. utilis*, *Geotrichum candidum*, and lactic acid bacteria significantly enhanced the protein content of apple pomace (Yang et al., 2022).

The experiment resulted in the selection of *B. coagulans* and four yeast strains for the subsequent optimization study, focusing on inoculum size and cultivation time. The optimization trial yielded excellent results in product formation, with *S. cerevisiae* and *K. marxianus* DSM 7238 performing the best in combination with *B. coagulans*, surpassing the *C. jadinii* strains. The bacteria-yeast co-cultures achieved 17.5 g of CDW, 6.9 g of crude protein, and 42.2 mg of B12/L of broth with *K. marxianus* DSM 7238, and 16.5 g of CDW, 6.3 g of crude protein, and 47.5 mg of B12/L of broth with *S. cerevisiae*, respectively. These maximum yields were obtained at the highest inoculum level of 10% (v/v) after 72 h of cultivation, except for vitamin B12 production with *K. marxianus* DSM 7238. Furthermore, the decreasing concentrations of acetic and lactic acids across all samples, along with a steady pH increase over the cultivation period, indicate active yeast metabolism of these acids, suggesting their potential for effective deacidification in mixed microbial cultures. Notably, in the *K. marxianus* DSM 7238 co-culture, pH significantly increased from 5.13 to 8.41, likely due to yeast shifting towards amino acid consumption once the primary carbon source was depleted, leading to ammonia or urea release and a subsequent pH rise, also known as alkalization (Ljungdahl and Daignan-Fornier, 2012; Ough et al., 1991). Overall, a larger inoculum size of 10% (v/v) resulted in higher sugar consumption, greater organic acid

utilization, and a more pronounced pH increase compared to lower inoculum sizes. Interestingly, most free sugars were depleted within just 24 h, particularly in co-cultures with *K. marxianus* DSM 7238 and *S. cerevisiae*. However, cell growth continued beyond 72 h, suggesting that microbial cultures were utilizing alternative nutrient sources.

In comparison with other studies utilizing similar plant-based feedstocks, marine algae-based substrates have been investigated for mycoprotein production. For instance, Landeta-Salgado et al. achieved 14 g CDW and 5.2 g of protein/L using a green algae-based medium with *Paradendryphiella salina* as the producing species (Landeta-Salgado et al., 2021). Similarly, they obtained 15 g CDW and 7.4 g of mycoprotein/L from a brown seaweed-based medium with *P. salina* (Salgado et al., 2021). Grass juice has also been explored as a feedstock. Sakarika and colleagues reported 3.7 g CDW/L when fermenting grass juice with *B. coagulans* DSM 2314 and *Cupriavidus necator* LMG 1199 in sequential manner (Sakarika et al., 2022). Stabnikova and coworkers achieved 8.2 g CDW and 3.7 g of crude protein/L using *S. cerevisiae* grown on plant waste-based media (Stabnikova et al., 2005). In another work, Carranza-Méndez et al. successfully produced 15.7 g CDW/L using an orange peel-based medium with *C. jadinii*, demonstrating deacidification as the pH increased from 3.2 to 4 during cultivation (Carranza-Méndez et al., 2022).

The subsequent exploratory analysis confirmed that the performance of the co-culture is primarily influenced by the yeast's ability to deacidify and detoxify the halophyte-based substrate, directly linking the deacidification process to CDW and crude protein production. This highlights yeast robustness as a key factor in product formation. However, compared to sole yeast cultivation on halophyte-based media, the addition of bacteria clearly reduced stress on yeast, resulting in absence of ethanol production and higher overall product formation. While the exact mechanism behind these interactions remains unknown, it is likely that a symbiotic relationship is established between the introduced cultures, ultimately enhancing their performance in a mutually beneficial way.

To conclude, this study demonstrates the potential of bacteria-yeast co-cultivation for improving microbial growth and postbiotic production on halophyte-based media. The ability of yeasts to deacidify and detoxify the substrate was a key driver of product formation, while bacterial co-culture mitigated stress, leading to higher yields. These findings highlight the importance of microbial interactions in alternative protein production and pave the way for further optimization and scale-up in sustainable bioprocessing applications.

5. Conclusion

This study demonstrates that combining bacteria and yeast can boost microbial growth, improve nutrient use, and increase postbiotic production when grown on halophyte-based media. In the initial screening, *S. cerevisiae* and *K. marxianus* DSM 7238 showed their strong ability to use available carbon sources present in hydrolysate, while other yeasts showed limited growth. In co-cultures, yeast played the main role in driving biomass and protein production, with *B. coagulans* ATCC 7050 further improving yields. In contrast, *L. plantarum* DSM 13272 inhibited yeast growth, likely due to lactic acid accumulation. Optimization trials revealed that higher inoculum levels and longer cultivation times substantially increased cell dry weight, protein, and vitamin B12 concentrations, achieving complete carbon source utilization, especially for *B. coagulans* ATCC 7050 with *K. marxianus* DSM 7238 or *S. cerevisiae*. A key finding was the important role of yeast-driven deacidification, which not only created better growth conditions but also likely encouraged the activity of other beneficial microbes. Comparisons with other studies utilizing alternative plant-based feedstocks, such as marine algae, grass juice, and fruit waste, revealed that the achieved biomass and protein yields in this study were more than competitive, underlining the suitability of halophyte hydrolysate for microbial cultivation. The findings suggest strong potential for further process optimization and

industrial-scale application in sustainable protein and postbiotic production. Overall, this research highlights the advantages of bacteria-yeast co-cultivation on halophyte hydrolysate in enhancing microbial growth and metabolic output in non-sterile conditions. Future studies should focus on refining cultivation parameters, exploring additional microbial combinations, and assessing large-scale feasibility by optimizing critical factors such as pH control, detoxification consistency, inoculation strategy, oxygen transfer efficiency, substrate uniformity, and microbial stability in non-sterile conditions to further develop this bioprocess for nutraceuticals production.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Stanislav Rudnyckij: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Oriol Varon Morales:** Validation, Investigation. **Paula Ramirez Sanchez Aguilera:** Validation, Investigation. **Sara Brandolini:** Validation, Investigation. **Steinunn Leifsdóttir:** Validation, Investigation. **Mette Hedegaard Thomsen:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Funding

This project has received funding from the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101084651 as part of the IGNITION project.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgment

The authors would like to thank Linda Birkebæk Madsen and Lilian Melo Bondig for their support and expertise during the analytical work. Additionally, the authors would like to thank Riasearch, Portugal for providing *Salicornia ramosissima* biomass.

Ethical approval

Not applicable.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- Abideen, Z., Ansari, R., Khan, M.A., 2011. Halophytes: potential source of lignocellulosic biomass for ethanol production. *Biomass Bioenergy* 35, 1818–1822. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biombioe.2011.01.023>.
- Accogli, R., Tomaselli, V., Drenzo, P., Perrino, E.V., Albanese, G., Urbano, M., Laghetti, G., 2023. Edible halophytes and halo-tolerant species in Apulia Region (Southeastern Italy): biogeography, traditional food use and potential sustainable crops. *Plants* 12, 549. <https://doi.org/10.3390/PLANTS12030549>.
- Agboola, J.O., Overland, M., Skrede, A., Hansen, J.Ø., 2021. Yeast as major protein-rich ingredient in aquafeeds: a review of the implications for aquaculture production. *Rev. Aquac.* 13, 949–970. <https://doi.org/10.1111/RAQ.12507>.
- Aggarwal, S., Sabharwal, V., Kaushik, P., Joshi, A., Aayushi, A., Suri, M., 2022. Postbiotics: from emerging concept to application. *Front Sustain Food Syst* 6, 887642. <https://doi.org/10.3389/FSUFS.2022.887642/BIBTEX>.
- Ahmadi, F., Mohammadkhani, N., Servati, M., 2022. Halophytes play important role in phytoremediation of salt-affected soils in the bed of Urmia Lake. *Iran. Sci Rep* 12, 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-16266-4>.
- Akter, S., Park, J.H., Jung, H.K., 2020. Potential health-promoting benefits of paraprobiotics. Inactivated probiotic cells. *J Microbiol Biotechnol* 30, 477. <https://doi.org/10.4014/JMB.1911.11019>.

- Alassali, A., Cybulska, I., Galvan, A.R., Thomsen, M.H., 2017. Wet fractionation of the succulent halophyte *Salicornia sinus-persica*, with the aim of low input (water saving) biorefining into bioethanol. *Appl. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* 101, 1769–1779. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S00253-016-8049-8/FIGURES/7>.
- Antolak, H., Piechota, D., Kucharska, A., 2021. Kombucha tea—A double power of bioactive compounds from tea and symbiotic culture of bacteria and yeasts (SCOBY). *Antioxidants* 10, 1541. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ANTIOX10101541>.
- Arif, S., Batool, A., Nazir, W., Khan, R.S., Khalid, N., 2019. Physicochemical characteristics nutritional properties and health benefits of sugarcane juice. *Non-alcoholic beverages: Volume 6. The Science of Beverages 227–257*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-815270-6.00008-6>.
- Attia-Ismail, S.A., 2008. Role of minerals in halophyte feeding to ruminants. *Trace Elem. Contam. Nutr.* 701–720. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9780470370124.CH27>.
- Aziz, I., Mujeeb, A., 2022. Halophytes for phytoremediation of hazardous metal(loid)s: a terse review on metal tolerance, bio-indication and hyperaccumulation. *J. Hazard. Mater.* 424, 127309. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JHAZMAT.2021.127309>.
- Babich, O., Ivanova, S., Michaud, P., Budenkova, E., Kashirskikh, E., Anokhova, V., Sukhikh, S., 2024. Fermentation of micro- and macroalgae as a way to produce value-added products. *Biotechnol. Rep.* 41, e00827. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.BTRE.2023.E00827>.
- Bourebaba, Y., Marycz, K., Mularczyk, M., Bourebaba, L., 2022. Postbiotics as potential new therapeutic agents for metabolic disorders management. *Biomed. Pharmacother.* 153, 113138. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.BIOPHA.2022.113138>.
- Campana, R., Tiboni, M., Maggi, F., Cappellacci, L., Cianfaglione, K., Morshedloo, M.R., Frangipani, E., Casettari, L., 2022. Comparative analysis of the antimicrobial activity of essential oils and their formulated microemulsions against foodborne pathogens and spoilage bacteria. *Antibiotics* 11, 447. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ANTIBIOTICS11040447/S1>.
- Carranza-Méndez, R.C., Chávez-González, M.L., Sepúlveda-Torre, L., Aguilar, C.N., Govea-Salas, M., Ramos-González, R., 2022. Production of single cell protein from orange peel residues by *Candida utilis*. *Biocatal. Agric. Biotechnol.* 40, 102298. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CBAB.2022.102298>.
- Cayenne, A., Turiós, A.E., Thomsen, M.H., Rocha, R.M., Papenbrock, J., Uellendahl, H., 2022. Halophytes as feedstock for biogas production: composition analysis and biomethane potential of *Salicornia* spp. plant material from hydroponic and seawater irrigation systems. *Fermentation* 8, 189. <https://doi.org/10.3390/FERMENTATION8040189>.
- Cheirsilp, B., Shoji, H., Shimizu, H., Shioya, S., 2003. Interactions between *Lactobacillus kefiranofaciens* and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* in mixed culture for kefir production. *J. Biosci. Bioeng.* 96, 279–284. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1389-1723\(03\)80194-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1389-1723(03)80194-9).
- Christiansen, A.H.C., Lyra, D.A., Jørgensen, H., 2021. Increasing the value of *Salicornia bigelovii* green biomass grown in a desert environment through biorefining. *Ind. Crop. Prod.* 160, 113105. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.INDCROP.2020.113105>.
- Chu, Y.T., Brown, P.B., 2022. Optimal dietary crude protein in commercial feeds for shrimp and halophytes in marine aquaponic bioflow systems. *Front. Mar. Sci.* 9, 824973. <https://doi.org/10.3389/FMARS.2022.824973/BIBTEX>.
- Coburn, J., Wells, M.S., Sheaffer, C.C., Ruan, R., Samac, D.A., 2021. Comparison of plant feedstocks and methods to recover leaf proteins from wet fractionation of alfalfa for potential use in aquaculture, poultry, and livestock feeds. *Agrosyst., Geosci. Environ.* 4, e20184. <https://doi.org/10.1002/AGG2.20184/WGROUP:STRING: PUBLICATION>.
- Correia, I., Antunes, M., Tecelão, C., Neves, M., Pires, C.L., Cruz, P.F., Rodrigues, M., Peralta, C.C., Pereira, C.D., Reboredo, F., Moreno, M.J., Brito, R.M.M., Ribeiro, V.S., Vaz, D.C., Campos, M.J., 2024. Nutritive value and bioactivities of a halophyte edible plant: *Crithmum maritimum* L. (Sea Fennel). *Plants* 13, 427. <https://doi.org/10.3390/PLANTS13030427/S1>.
- Cosme, F., Inês, A., Vilela, A., 2022. Consumer's acceptability and health consciousness of probiotic and prebiotic of non-dairy products. *Food Res. Int.* 151, 110842. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FOODRES.2021.110842>.
- Cybulska, I., Chaturvedi, T., Brudecki, G.P., Kádár, Z., Meyer, A.S., Baldwin, R.M., Thomsen, M.H., 2014. Chemical characterization and hydrothermal pretreatment of *Salicornia bigelovii* straw for enhanced enzymatic hydrolysis and bioethanol production. *Bioresour. Technol.* 153, 165–172. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.BIORTECH.2013.11.071>.
- Czerucka, D., Piche, T., Rampal, P., 2007. Review article: yeast as probiotics – *Saccharomyces boulardii*. *Aliment. Pharmacol. Ther.* 26, 767–778. <https://doi.org/10.1111/J.1365-2036.2007.03442.X>.
- Da, M., Sun, J., Ma, C., Li, D., Dong, L., Wang, L.S., Chen, F., 2024. Postbiotics: enhancing human health with a novel concept. *eFood* 5, e180. <https://doi.org/10.1002/EFD2.180>.
- de Oliveira Junqueira, A.C., de Melo Pereira, G.V., Coral Medina, J.D., Alvear, M.C.R., Rosero, R., de Carvalho Neto, D.P., Enríquez, H.G., Soccol, C.R., 2019. First description of bacterial and fungal communities in Colombian coffee beans fermentation analysed using Illumina-based amplicon sequencing. *Sci. Rep.* 9, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-45002-8>.
- Delmoitié, B., Sakarika, M., Rabaey, K., De Wever, H., Regueira, A., 2025. Tailoring non-axenic lactic acid fermentation from cheese whey permeate targeting a flexible lactic acid platform. *J. Environ. Manage.* 373, 123529. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JENVMAN.2024.123529>.
- Demirgul, F., Simsek, O., Sagdic, O., 2022. Amino acid, mineral, vitamin B contents and bioactivities of extracts of yeasts isolated from sourdough. *Food Biosci.* 50, 102040. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FBIO.2022.102040>.
- Eggleston, G., Triplett, A., Bett-Garber, K., Boue, S., Bechtel, P., 2022. Macronutrient and mineral contents in sweet sorghum syrups compared to other commercial syrup sweeteners. *J. Agric. Food Res.* 7, 100276. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JAFR.2022.100276>.
- Essaidi, I., Brahmi, Z., Snoussi, A., Ben Haj Koubaier, H., Casabianca, H., Abe, N., El Omri, A., Chaabouni, M.M., Bouzouita, N., 2013. Phytochemical investigation of Tunisian *Salicornia herbacea* L., antioxidant, antimicrobial and cytochrome P450 (CYPs) inhibitory activities of its methanol extract. *Food Control* 32, 125–133. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FOODCONT.2012.11.006>.
- Ferreira, I., de Sousa Melo, D., Menezes, A.G.T., Fonseca, H.C., de Assis, B.B.T., Ramos, C. L., Magnani, M., Dias, D.R., Schwann, R.F., 2022. Evaluation of potentially probiotic yeasts and *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum* in co-culture for the elaboration of a functional plant-based fermented beverage. *Food Res. Int.* 160, 111697. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FOODRES.2022.111697>.
- Figueroa-Hernández, C., Mota-Gutiérrez, J., Ferrocino, I., Hernández-Estrada, Z.J., González-Ríos, O., Coccolin, L., Suárez-Quiroz, M.L., 2019. The challenges and perspectives of the selection of starter cultures for fermented cocoa beans. *Int. J. Food Microbiol.* 301, 41–50. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.IJFOODMICRO.2019.05.002>.
- Fijan, S., 2014. Microorganisms with claimed probiotic properties: an overview of recent literature. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* 11, 4745. <https://doi.org/10.3390/IJERPH110504745>.
- Flowers, T.J., Colmer, T.D., 2008. Salinity tolerance in halophytes. *New Phytol.* 179, 945–963. <https://doi.org/10.1111/J.1469-8137.2008.02531.X>.
- Fredsgaard, M., Hultko, L.S.S., Chaturvedi, T., Thomsen, M.H., 2021. Process simulation and techno-economic assessment of *Salicornia* sp. based jet fuel refinery through *Hermetia illucens* sugars-to-lipids conversion and HEFA route. *Biomass Bioenergy* 150, 106142. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.BIOMBIOE.2021.106142>.
- Fredsgaard, M., Tchoumtchoua, J., Kohnen, S., Chaturvedi, T., Thomsen, M.H., 2023. Isolation of polyphenols from aqueous extract of the halophyte *Salicornia ramosissima*. *Molecules* 29, 220. <https://doi.org/10.3390/MOLECULES29010220>.
- Gaffey, J., Rajauria, G., McMahon, H., Ravindran, R., Dominguez, C., Ambye-Jensen, M., Souza, M.F., Meers, E., Aragonés, M.M., Skunca, D., Sanders, J.P.M., 2023. Green Biorefinery systems for the production of climate-smart sustainable products from grasses, legumes and green crop residues. *Biotechnol. Adv.* 66, 108168. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.BIOTECHADV.2023.108168>.
- García, G., Soto, J., Díaz, A., Barreto, J., Soto, C., Pérez, A.B., Boffill, S., Gutiérrez, Á., Cano, R. de J., 2024. Clinical and In Vitro Safety of *Heyndrickxia coagulans* AO 1167B: a double-blind placebo-controlled trial. *Microorganisms* 12, 2584. <https://doi.org/10.3390/MICROORGANISMS12122584>.
- Giannoulis, K.D., Bartzialis, D., Skoufogianni, E., Gintsioudis, I., Danalatos, N.G., 2022. Could a legume-switchgrass sod-seeding system increase forage productivity? *Plants* 11, 2970. <https://doi.org/10.3390/PLANTS11212970>.
- Giordano, R., Saii, Z., Fredsgaard, M., Hultko, L.S.S., Poulsen, T.B.G., Thomsen, M.E., Henneberg, N., Zucolotto, S.M., Arendt-Nielsen, L., Papenbrock, J., Thomsen, M.H., Stensballe, A., 2021. Pharmacological insights into halophyte bioactive extract action on anti-inflammatory, pain relief and antibiotics-type mechanisms. *Molecules* 26, 3140. <https://doi.org/10.3390/MOLECULES26113140>.
- González-Orozco, B.D., Kosmerl, E., Jiménez-Flores, R., Alvarez, V.B., 2023. Enhanced probiotic potential of *Lactobacillus kefiranofaciens* OSU-BDGOA1 through co-culture with *Kluyveromyces marxianus* bdgo-ym6. *Front. Microbiol.* 14, 1236634. <https://doi.org/10.3389/FMICB.2023.1236634/BIBTEX>.
- Guo, X., Aganovic, K., Bindrich, U., Juadjar, A., Hertel, C., Ebert, E., Macke, J., Große, Geil, C., Heinz, V., 2022. Extraction of protein from juice blend of grass and clover pressed by a pilot pressing facility combined with a pulsed electric field treatment. *Future Foods* 6, 100173. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FUFO.2022.100173>.
- Guo, Y., Xiong, Z., Zhai, H., Wang, Y., Qi, Q., Hou, J., 2025. The advances in creating Crabtree-negative *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and the application for chemicals biosynthesis. *FEMS Yeast Res.* 25, 14. <https://doi.org/10.1093/FEMSYR/FOAF014>.
- GVR, 2025. Nutraceuticals Market Size And Share, 2030 [WWW Document]. URL <https://www.grandviewresearch.com/industry-analysis/nutraceuticals-market> (accessed 2.7.25).
- Hanif, A., Ejaz, U., Ansari, I., Sohail, M., Samma, M.K., Siddiqi, M., Suleman, F., Karim, M., 2024. Potential Application of *Suaeda frutescens* and *Cressa cretica* Biomass as a Substrate for Pectinase Production by *Geotrichum candidum*. *Arab J Sci Eng* 49, 59–66. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S13369-023-08000-7/METRICS>.
- Healy, L.E., Zhu, X., Kakagianni, M., Pojary, M.M., Sullivan, C., Tiwari, U., Curtin, J., Sun, D.W., Tiwari, B.K., 2023. Fermentation of brown seaweeds *Alaria esculenta* and *Saccharina latissima* for new product development using *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum*, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and kombucha SCOBY. *Algal Res.* 76, 103322. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ALGAL.2023.103322>.
- Hill, C., Guarner, F., Reid, G., Gibson, G.R., Merenstein, D.J., Pot, B., Morelli, L., Canani, R.B., Flint, H.J., Salminen, S., Calder, P.C., Sanders, M.E., 2014. The international scientific association for probiotics and prebiotics consensus statement on the scope and appropriate use of the term probiotic. *Nat. Rev. Gastroenterol. Hepatol.* 11, 506–514. [10.1038/NRGASTRO.2014.66](https://doi.org/10.1038/NRGASTRO.2014.66); [SUBJMETA=1503,2135,2741,565,692,698,699,700;KWRD=GASTROINTESTINAL +DISEASES, MICROBIOTA, THERAPEUTICS](https://doi.org/10.1038/NRGASTRO.2014.66).
- Hu, W., Zhou, L., Chen, Hong, J., 2022. Conversion sweet sorghum biomass to produce value-added products. *Biotechnol. Biofuels Bioprod.* 15, 72. <https://doi.org/10.1186/S13068-022-02170-6>.
- Hugot, C., Poirier, M., Spatz, M., Da Costa, G., Michaudel, C., Lapiere, A., Danne, C., Martin, V., Langella, P., Sokol, H., Michel, M.-L., Boyaval, P., Richard, M.L., 2023. Cyberlindnera Jadinii and *Kluyveromyces lactis*, two fungi used in food processes, have potential probiotic effects on gut inflammation. *mSystems* 8, e00841–e00923. <https://doi.org/10.1128/MSYSTEMS.00841-23>.
- Hultko, L.S.S., 2023. Exploring the Potential of Halophyte Biomass for Green Biorefinery Applications. PhD thesis. Aalborg University, Esbjerg.

- Hulkko, L.S.S., Chaturvedi, T., Thomsen, M.H., 2022. Extraction and quantification of chlorophylls, carotenoids, phenolic compounds, and vitamins from halophyte biomass. *Appl. Sci.* 12, 840. <https://doi.org/10.3390/APPL12020840>.
- Hulkko, L.S.S., Rocha, R.M., Trentin, R., Fredsgaard, M., Chaturvedi, T., Custódio, L., Thomsen, M.H., 2023a. Bioactive extracts from *Salicornia ramosissima* J. Woods biorefinery as a source of ingredients for high-value industries. *Plants* 12, 1251. <https://doi.org/10.3390/PLANTS12061251>.
- Hulkko, L.S.S., Turcios, A.E., Kohlen, S., Chaturvedi, T., Papenbrock, J., Thomsen, M.H., 2022b. Cultivation and characterisation of *Salicornia europaea*, *Tripolium pannonicum* and *Crithmum maritimum* biomass for green biorefinery applications. *Sci. Rep.* 2022 12:1 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-24865-4>.
- Jofre, F.M., Hernández-Pérez, A.F., Santos, J.C. dos, Felipe, M. das G. de A., 2021. Use of dry yeast biomass as a new approach for detoxification of hemicellulosic hydrolysates aiming to xylitol production. *Ind. Crops Prod.* 170, 113812. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.INDCROP.2021.113812>.
- Kallur, R.K., Madapur, S., Mathur, A., 2022. High-quality draft genome sequence and characterization of ProBC Plus *Weizmannia (bacillus) coagulans* LMG S-31876. *Microbiol. Resour. Announ.* 12, e01018–e01022. <https://doi.org/10.1128/MRA.01018-22>.
- Karunanithy, C., Muthukumarappan, K., 2010. Influence of extruder temperature and screw speed on pretreatment of corn stover while varying enzymes and their ratios. *Appl. Biochem. Biotechnol.* 162, 264–279. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S12010-009-8757-Y/TABLES/4>.
- Keskin, P., Kılıç Kanak, E., Öztürk Yılmaz, S., 2024. Assessment of the probiotic properties of *Yarrowia lipolytica* isolated from cold-pressed olive oil. *Microorganisms* 12. <https://doi.org/10.3390/MICROORGANISMS12091905>.
- Khushboo, Karnwal, A., Malik, T., 2023. Characterization and selection of probiotic lactic acid bacteria from different dietary sources for development of functional foods. *Front. Microbiol.* 14, 1170725. <https://doi.org/10.3389/FMICB.2023.1170725/BIBTEX>.
- Koegel, R.G., Sreenath, H.K., Straub, R.J., 1999. Alfalfa fiber as a feedstock for ethanol and organic acids. Twentieth Symposium on Biotechnology for Fuels and Chemicals 105–115. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4612-1604-9_10.
- Ksouri, R., Megdiche, W., Falleh, H., Trabelsi, N., Boulaaba, M., Smaoui, A., Abdely, C., 2008. Influence of biological, environmental and technical factors on phenolic content and antioxidant activities of Tunisian halophytes. *C. R. Biol.* 331, 865–873. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CRV.2008.07.024>.
- Kucheryavskiy, S., 2020. mdatools – R package for chemometrics. *Chemometr. Intell. Lab. Syst.* 198, 103937. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CHEMOLAB.2020.103937>.
- Kumar, R., Singh, U., Tiwari, A., Tiwari, P., Sahu, J.K., Sharma, S., 2023. Vitamin B12: strategies for enhanced production, fortified functional food products and health benefits. *Process Biochem.* 127, 44–55. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.PROCBIO.2023.02.002>.
- Landeta-Salgado, C., Cicatiello, P., Lienqueo, M.E., 2021. Mycoprotein and hydrophobin like protein produced from marine fungi *Paradenryphiella salina* in submerged fermentation with green seaweed *Ulva* spp. *Algal Res.* 56, 102314. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ALGAL.2021.102314>.
- Larnaudie, V., Ferrari, M.D., Lareo, C., 2022. Switchgrass as an alternative biomass for ethanol production in a biorefinery: perspectives on technology, economics and environmental sustainability. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 158, 112115. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.RSER.2022.112115>.
- Lean, I.J., Celi, P., Raadsma, H., McNamara, J., Rabiee, A.R., 2012. Effects of dietary crude protein on fertility: Meta-analysis and meta-regression. *Anim. Feed Sci. Technol.* 171, 31–42. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ANIFEEDSCI.2011.09.017>.
- Liang, J., Li, C., Chen, Z., Guo, F., Dou, J., Wang, T., Xu, Z.S., 2024. Progress of research and application of *Heyndrickxia coagulans* (*Bacillus coagulans*) as probiotic bacteria. *Front. Cell Infect. Microbiol.* 14, 1415790. <https://doi.org/10.3389/FMICB.2024.1415790/BIBTEX>.
- Limbach, J.R., Espinosa, C.D., Perez-Calvo, E., Stein, H.H., 2021. Effect of dietary crude protein level on growth performance, blood characteristics, and indicators of intestinal health in weanling pigs. *J. Anim. Sci.* 99. <https://doi.org/10.1093/JAS/SKAB166>.
- Liu, J., Shi, P., Ahmad, S., Yin, C., Liu, X., Liu, Y., Zhang, H., Xu, Q., Yan, H., Li, Q., 2019. Co-culture of *Bacillus coagulans* and *Candida utilis* efficiently treats *Lactobacillus* fermentation wastewater. *AMB Express* 9, 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1186/S13568-019-0743-3/FIGURES/7>.
- Ljungdahl, P.O., Daignan-Fornier, B., 2012. Regulation of amino acid, nucleotide, and phosphate metabolism in *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*. *Genetics* 190, 885. <https://doi.org/10.1534/GENETICS.111.133306>.
- Maftei, N.M., Raileanu, C.R., Balta, A.A., Ambrose, L., Boev, M., Marin, D.B., Lisa, E.L., 2024. The potential impact of probiotics on human health: an update on their health-promoting properties. *Microorganisms* 12, 234. <https://doi.org/10.3390/MICROORGANISMS12020234>.
- Maoloni, A., Cardinali, F., Milanović, V., Osimani, A., Verdenelli, M.C., Coman, M.M., Aquilanti, L., 2022. Exploratory study for probiotic enrichment of a sea fennel (*Crithmum maritimum* L.) preserve in brine. *Foods* 2022, 11,, 2219 2219. <https://doi.org/10.3390/FOODS11152219>.
- Mariotti, F., Tomé, D., Mirand, P.P., 2008. Converting nitrogen into protein—beyond 6.25 and Jones' factors. *Crit. Rev. Food Sci. Nutr.* 48, 177–184. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10408390701279749>.
- Markowski, J., Baron, A., Mieszczakowska, M., Plocharski, W., 2009. Chemical composition of French and Polish cloudy apple juices. *J. Hort. Sci. Biotechnol.* 84, 68–74. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14620316.2009.11512598>.
- Maske, B.L., de Melo Pereira, G. V., da S. Vale, A., de Carvalho Neto, D.P., Karp, S.G., Viesser, J.A., De Dea Lindner, J., Pagnoncelli, M.G., Soccol, V.T., Soccol, C.R., 2021. A review on enzyme-producing lactobacilli associated with the human digestive process: From metabolism to application. *Enzyme Microb. Technol.* 149, 109836. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENZMICTEC.2021.109836>.
- Mathur, H., Beresford, T.P., Cotter, P.D., 2020. Health benefits of lactic acid bacteria (LAB) fermentates. *Nutrients* 12, 1679. <https://doi.org/10.3390/NU12061679>.
- Medeiros, A.B.P., de Matos, M.E., de Pinho Monteiro, A., de Carvalho, J.C., Soccol, C.R., 2017. Cachaça and Rum. Current developments in biotechnology and bioengineering: food and beverages industry 451–468. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-444-63666-9.00016-9>.
- Mejía-Pitta, A., Broset, E., de la Fuente-Núñez, C., 2021. Probiotic engineering strategies for the heterologous production of antimicrobial peptides. *Adv Drug Deliv. Rev.* 176, 113863. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ADDR.2021.113863>.
- Meng, D., Zhang, F., Jia, W., Jiao, J., Zhang, Y., 2024. Understanding the health implications of furan and its derivatives in thermally processed foods: occurrence, toxicology, and mixture analysis. *Curr. Opin. Food Sci.* 57, 101151. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.COFS.2024.101151>.
- Monção, M., Thoresen, P.P., Wretborn, T., Lange, H., Rova, U., Christakopoulos, P., Matsakas, L., 2023. A novel biorefinery concept based on marginally used halophyte biomass. *Sustain. Energy Fuels* 7, 3902–3918. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D3SE00458A>.
- Monção, M., Wretborn, T., Rova, U., Matsakas, L., Christakopoulos, P., 2022. *Salicornia dolichostachya* organosolv fractionation: towards establishing a halophyte biorefinery. *RSC Adv.* 12, 28599–28607. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D2RA04432C>.
- Moradi, M., Molaei, R., Guimarães, J.T., 2021. A review on preparation and chemical analysis of postbiotics from lactic acid bacteria. *Enzyme Microb. Technol.* 143, 109722. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENZMICTEC.2020.109722>.
- Moradi, R., Nosrati, R., Zare, H., Tahmasebi, T., Saderi, H., Owlia, P., 2018. Screening and characterization of in-vitro probiotic criteria of *Saccharomyces* and *Kluyveromyces* strains. *Iran J. Microbiol.* 10, 123.
- Morrison, D.J., Preston, T., 2016. Formation of short chain fatty acids by the gut microbiota and their impact on human metabolism. *Gut. Microbes* 7, 189. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19490976.2015.1134082>.
- Narendranath, N.V., Thomas, K.C., Ingledew, W.M., 2001. Acetic acid and lactic acid inhibition of growth of *saccharomyces cerevisiae* by different mechanisms. *J. Am. Soc. Brewing Chem.* 59, 187–194. <https://doi.org/10.1094/ASBCJ-59-0187>.
- Nguyen, M., Ferge, K.K., Vaughn, A.R., Burney, W., Teng, L.H., Pan, A., Nguyen, V., Sivamani, R.K., 2020. Probiotic supplementation and food intake and knowledge among patients and consumers. *Probiot. Antimicrob. Proteins* 12, 824–833. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S12602-019-09602-0/TABLES/4>.
- Nguyen, N.K., Nguyen, P.B., Nguyen, H.T., Le, P.H., 2015. Screening the optimal ratio of symbiosis between isolated yeast and acetic acid bacteria strain from traditional kombucha for high-level production of gluconic acid. *LWT - Food Sci. Technol.* 64, 1149–1155. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.LWT.2015.07.018>.
- Ough, C.S., Huang, Z., An, D., Stevens, J., 1991. Amino acid uptake by four commercial yeasts at two different temperatures of growth and fermentation: effects on urea excretion and reabsorption. *Am. J. Enol. Vitic.* 42, 26–40. <https://doi.org/10.5344/AJEV.1991.42.1.26>.
- Panagiotopoulos, I.A., Bakker, R.R., de Vrije, T., Claassen, P.A.M., Koukios, E.G., 2013. Integration of first and second generation biofuels: Fermentative hydrogen production from wheat grain and straw. *Bioresour. Technol.* 128, 345–350. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.BIORTECH.2012.09.083>.
- Pap, N., Granato, D., Järvenpää, E., Tienaho, J., Marnila, P., Hellström, J., Pihlava, J.M., Franco, M., Stefański, T., Rinne, M., 2024. Biorefining of legume and grass biomass: technological properties and bioactivities of the green juice. *Future Foods* 9, 100331. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FUFO.2024.100331>.
- Passoth, V., Sandgren, M., 2019. Biofuel production from straw hydrolysates: current achievements and perspectives. *Appl. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* 103, 5105–5116. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S00253-019-09863-3/METRICS>.
- Pérez-Alvarado, O., Zepeda-Hernández, A., García-Amezquita, L.E., Requena, T., Vinderola, G., García-Cayuela, T., 2022. Role of lactic acid bacteria and yeasts in sourdough fermentation during breadmaking: evaluation of postbiotic-like components and health benefits. *Front. Microbiol.* 13, 969460. <https://doi.org/10.3389/FMICB.2022.969460/BIBTEX>.
- Persic, M., Mikulic-Petkovsek, M., Slatnar, A., Veberic, R., 2017. Chemical composition of apple fruit, juice and pomace and the correlation between phenolic content, enzymatic activity and browning. *LWT - Food Sci. Technol.* 82, 23–31. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.LWT.2017.04.017>.
- Petersen, M.Ø., Larsen, J., Thomsen, M.H., 2009. Optimization of hydrothermal pretreatment of wheat straw for production of bioethanol at low water consumption without addition of chemicals. *Biomass Bioenergy* 33, 834–840. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.BIOMBIOE.2009.01.004>.
- Pihurov, M., Păcularu-Burada, B., Coțârleț, M., Grigore-Gurgu, L., Borda, D., Stănciuc, N., Kluz, M., Băhrim, G.E., 2023. Kombucha and water kefir grains microbiomes' symbiotic contribution to postbiotics enhancement. *Foods* 12, 2581. <https://doi.org/10.3390/FOODS12132581>.
- Pires-Cabral, P., Pires-Cabral, P., Quintas, C., 2022. *Salicornia ramosissima* as a salt substitute in the fermentation of white cabbage. *J. Food Sci. Technol.* 59, 597–605. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S13197-021-05047-Y/METRICS>.
- Ponomarova, O., Gabrielli, N., Sévin, D.C., Müller, M., Zirngibl, K., Bulyha, K., Andrejev, S., Kafkia, E., Typas, A., Sauer, U., Ralsler, M., Patil, K.R., 2017. Yeast creates a niche for symbiotic lactic acid bacteria through nitrogen overflow. *Cell Syst.* 5, 345–357.e6. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CELS.2017.09.002/ASSET/8DEA28F3-68A3-431C-8D8C-34D0107DA57A/MAIN.ASSETS/GR6.JPG>.
- Ponzio, A., Rebecchi, A., Zivoli, R., Morelli, L., 2024. Reuterin, phenyllactic acid, and exopolysaccharides as main antifungal molecules produced by lactic acid bacteria: a scoping review. *Foods* 13, 752. <https://doi.org/10.3390/FOODS13050752>.
- R Core Team, 2020. R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing.

- Rocha, G.J. de M., Nascimento, V.M., Gonçalves, A.R., Silva, V.F.N., Martín, C., 2015. Influence of mixed sugarcane bagasse samples evaluated by elemental and physical–chemical composition. *Ind. Crops Prod.* 64, 52–58. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2014.11.003>.
- Rudnyckij, S., Chaturvedi, T., Thomsen, M.H., 2024. Microbial biomass production from enzymatically saccharified organic municipal waste and present microbial inhibitors. *Biomass Convers. Biorefin.* 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S13399-024-05980-W/TABLES/2>.
- Rudnyckij, S., Chaturvedi, T., Thomsen, M.H., 2023. Low-dosage enzymatic hydrolysis of organic municipal waste for sugar and ethanol production. *Biomass Convers. Biorefin.* 1, 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S13399-023-04858-7/TABLES/8>.
- Rudnyckij, S., Thomsen, M.H., 2025. Probiotics and postbiotics derived from saline/marine plant-based feedstocks. *Probiot. Antimicrob. Proteins* 2025, 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S12602-025-10617-Z>.
- Sadeghi, A., Ebrahimi, M., Shahryari, S., Kharazmi, M.S., Jafari, S.M., 2022. Food applications of probiotic yeasts; focusing on their techno-functional, postbiotic and protective capabilities. *Trends Food Sci. Technol.* 128, 278–295. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.TIFS.2022.08.018>.
- Sakarika, M., Delmoitié, B., Ntagia, E., Chatzigiannidou, I., Gabet, X., Ganigué, R., Rabaey, K., 2022. Production of microbial protein from fermented grass. *Chem. Eng. J.* 433, 133631. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CEJ.2021.133631>.
- Salgado, C.L., Muñoz, R., Blanco, A., Lienqueo, M.E., 2021. Valorization and upgrading of the nutritional value of seaweed and seaweed waste using the marine fungi *Paradendryphiella salina* to produce mycoprotein. *Algal Res.* 53, 102135. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ALGAL.2020.102135>.
- Salminen, S., Collado, M.C., Endo, A., Hill, C., Lebeer, S., Quigley, E.M.M., Sanders, M.E., Shamir, R., Swann, J.R., Szajewska, H., Vinderola, G., 2021. The International Scientific Association of Probiotics and Prebiotics (ISAPP) consensus statement on the definition and scope of postbiotics. *Nat. Rev. Gastroenterol. Hepatol.* 2021 18:9 18, 649–667. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41575-021-00440-6>.
- Santamaría-Fernández, M., Ambye-Jensen, M., Damborg, V.K., Lübeck, M., 2019. Demonstration-scale protein recovery by lactic acid fermentation from grass clover – a single case of the production of protein concentrate and press cake silage for animal feeding trials. *Biofuels, Bioprod. Bioref.* 13, 502–513. <https://doi.org/10.1002/BBB.1957>.
- Santamaría-Fernández, M., Molinuevo-Salces, B., Kiel, P., Steinfeldt, S., Uellendahl, H., Lübeck, M., 2017. Lactic acid fermentation for refining proteins from green crops and obtaining a high quality feed product for monogastric animals. *J. Clean Prod.* 162, 875–881. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JCLEPRO.2017.06.115>.
- Sarıtaş, S., Duman, H., Karav, S., 2024. Nutritional and functional aspects of fermented algae. *Int. J. Food Sci. Technol.* 59, 5270–5284. <https://doi.org/10.1111/IJFS.17297>.
- Seo, S.H., Park, S.E., Kim, E.J., Cho, K.M., Kwon, S.J., Son, H.S., 2020. Effect of fungi on metabolite changes in kimchi during fermentation. *Molecules* 25, 5040. <https://doi.org/10.3390/MOLECULES25215040>.
- Shabbirahmed, A.M., Haldar, D., Dey, P., Patel, A.K., Singhania, R.R., Dong, C.D., Purkait, M.K., 2022. Sugarcane bagasse into value-added products: a review. *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.* <https://doi.org/10.1007/S11356-022-21889-1>.
- Shahbandeh, M., 2025. Statista: Global probiotics estimated market value 2022-2027. [WWW Document]. URL <https://www.statista.com/statistics/821259/global-probiotics-market-value/> (accessed 2.7.25).
- Sieuwerts, S., Bron, P.A., Smid, E.J., 2018. Mutually stimulating interactions between lactic acid bacteria and Saccharomyces cerevisiae in sourdough fermentation. *LWT* 90, 201–206. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.LWT.2017.12.022>.
- Sluiter, A., Hames, B., Hyman, D., Payne, C., Ruiz, R., Scarlata, C., Sluiter, J., Templeton, D., Wolfe, J., 2008. Determination of Total Solids in Biomass and Total Dissolved Solids in Liquid Process Samples Laboratory Analytical Procedure (LAP) Issue Date: 3/31/2008.
- Sluiter, A., Hames, B., Ruiz, R., Scarlata, C., Sluiter, J., Templeton, D., 2006. Determination of Sugars, Byproducts, and Degradation Products in Liquid Fraction Process Samples: Laboratory Analytical Procedure (LAP); Issue Date: 12/08/2006.
- Stabnikova, O., Wang, J.Y., Bo Ding, H., Joo-HwaTay, 2005. Biotransformation of vegetable and fruit processing wastes into yeast biomass enriched with selenium. *Bioresour. Technol.* 96, 747–751. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.BIORTECH.2004.06.022>.
- Stadie, J., Gultiz, A., Ehrmann, M.A., Vogel, R.F., 2013. Metabolic activity and symbiotic interactions of lactic acid bacteria and yeasts isolated from water kefir. *Food Microbiol.* 35, 92–98. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FM.2013.03.009>.
- Torres-Guardado, R., Esteve-Zarzoso, B., Reguant, C., Bordons, A., 2021. Microbial interactions in alcoholic beverages. *International Microbiology* 2021 25:1 25, 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S10123-021-00200-1>.
- Vergara, S.C., Leiva, M.J., Mestre, M.V., Vazquez, F., Nally, M.C., Maturano, Y.P., 2023. Non-saccharomyces yeast probiotics: revealing relevance and potential. *FEMS Yeast Res.* 23, 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1093/FEMSYR/FOAD041>.
- Viljoen, B.C., 2001. The interaction between yeasts and bacteria in dairy environments. *Int. J. Food Microbiol.* 69, 37–44. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1605\(01\)00570-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1605(01)00570-0).
- Vorob'eva, L.I., Khodzhaev, E.Y., Rogozhin, E.A., Cherdyntseva, T.A., Netrusov, A.I., 2016. Characterization of extracellular yeast peptide factors and their stress-protective effect on probiotic lactic acid bacteria. *Microbiology (Russian Federation)* 85, 411–419. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S0026261716040160/METRICS>.
- Wang, C., Song, X., Li, C., He, L., Wang, X., Zeng, X., 2023. Mixed fermentation with *Lactobacillus plantarum*, *Bifidobacterium animalis subsp. lactis* and *Candida utilis* improves the fermentation quality of Hong Suan Tang. *Food Chem.* 402, 134488. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FOODCHEM.2022.134488>.
- Wang, Y., Luo, Y., Luo, L., Zhang, H., Liao, Y., Gou, C., 2021. Enhancement of the nutritional value of fermented corn stover as ruminant feed using the fungi *Pleurotus spp.* *Sci. Rep.* 11, 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1038/S41598-021-90236-0>; SUBJMETA=1647,61,631;KWRD=BIOLOGICAL+TECHNIQUES, BIOTECHNOLOGY.
- Wei, T., Simko, V., Michael Levy, Yihui Xie, Yan Jin, Jeff Zemla, Moritz Freidank, Jun Cai, Tomas Protivinsky, 2024. corrpilot: Visualization of a Correlation Matrix. CRAN: Contributed Packages. <https://doi.org/10.32614/CRAN.PACKAGE.CORRPILOT>.
- Wu, L.C., Siebert, K.J., 2002. Characterization of haze-active proteins in apple juice. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 50, 3828–3834. <https://doi.org/10.1021/JF011471N/ASSET/IMAGES/LARGE/JF011471NF00007.JPEG>.
- Xu, J., Peng, S., Xiong, Y., Zheng, Z., Liu, M., Xu, J., Chen, W., Liu, M., Kong, J., Wang, C., Wang, Y., Rao, L., Zhao, L., Liao, X., 2024. A review on fermented vegetables: Microbial community and potential upgrading strategy via inoculated fermentation. *Compr. Rev. Food Sci. Food Saf.* 23, e13362. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1541-4337.13362>.
- Yadav, S., Mishra, A., Jha, B., 2018. Elevated CO2 leads to carbon sequestration by modulating C4 photosynthesis pathway enzyme (PDK) in *Suaeda monoica* and *S. frutescens*. *J. Photochem. Photobiol. B* 178, 310–315. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JPHOTOB.2017.11.022>.
- Yang, X., Hu, W., Xiu, Z., Jiang, A., Yang, X., Saren, G., Ji, Y., Guan, Y., Feng, K., 2020. Microbial community dynamics and metabolome changes during spontaneous fermentation of northeast sauerkraut from different households. *Front. Microbiol.* 11, 578106. <https://doi.org/10.3389/FMICB.2020.01878/BIBTEX>.
- Yang, Z., Jiang, L., Zhang, M., Deng, Y., Suo, W., Zhang, H., Wang, C., Li, H., 2022. Bioconversion of apple pomace into microbial protein feed based on extrusion pretreatment. *Appl. Biochem. Biotechnol.* 194, 1496–1509. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S12010-021-03727-1/TABLES/2>.
- Yassien, E.E., Hamed, M.M., Abdelmohsen, U.R., Hassan, H.M., Gazwi, H.S.S., 2021. In vitro antioxidant, antibacterial, and antihyperlipidemic potential of ethanolic *Avicennia marina* leaves extract supported by metabolic profiling. *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.* 28, 27207–27217. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S11356-021-12496-7/FIGURES/4>.
- Zhang, D.D., Liu, J.L., Jiang, T.M., Li, L., Fang, G.Z., Liu, Y.P., Chen, L.J., 2017. Influence of *Kluyveromyces marxianus* on proteins, peptides, and amino acids in *Lactobacillus-fermented milk*. *Food Sci. Biotechnol.* 26, 739–748. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S10068-017-0094-2/TABLES/3>.
- Zoumpourtikoudi, V., Pyrgelis, N., Chatzigrigoriou, M., Tasakis, R.N., Touraki, M., 2018. Interactions among yeast and probiotic bacteria enhance probiotic properties and metabolism offering augmented protection to *Artemia franciscana* against *Vibrio anguillarum*. *Microb. Pathog.* 125, 497–506. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.MICPATH.2018.10.022>.